

H2020 - INDUSTRIAL LEADERSHIP - Leadership in enabling and industrial technologies - Information and Communication Technologies (ICT)

ICT-11-2017 Collective Awareness Platforms for Sustainability and Social Innovation – Innovation Action (IA)

CHILD
RESCUE

Collective Awareness Platform for Missing Children Investigation and Rescue

D4.6 - ChildRescue Pilot Evaluation and Lessons Learnt

Workpackage: WP4 – Missing Persons Cases Piloting and Evaluation

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Status: Final

Date: 31/12/2020

Version: 1.00

Classification: Public

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The ChildRescue project is co-funded by the Horizon 2020 Programme of the European Union. This document reflects only authors' views. The EC is not liable for any use that may be done of the information contained therein

ChildRescue Project Profile

Grant Agreement No.: 780938

Acronym:	ChildRescue
Title:	Collective Awareness Platform for Missing Children Investigation and Rescue
URL:	http://www.childrescue.eu
Start Date:	01/01/2018
Duration:	36 months

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Document History

Version	Date	Author (Partner)	Remarks
0.10	13/10/2020	FRA-UAS	Table of Contents
0.20	25/11/2020	FRA-UAS	Input
0.21	29/11/2020	REDCROSS	Input
0.22	30/11/2020	SLG, UBITECH, S5	Input
0.23	30/11/2020	NTUA	Input
0.24	01/12/2020	ChildFocus	Input
0.25	01/12/2020	SoC	Input
0.26	02/12/2020	MCE	Input
0.30	3/12/2020	FRA-UAS	Consolidation
0.31	07/12/2020	ChildFocus	Changes
0.40	09/12/2020	SLG, UBITECH, S5	1st Internal Review
0.41	14/12/2020	NTUA	2nd Internal Review
0.50	28/12/2020	FRA-UAS	Consolidation of reviews
0.60	29/12/2020	NTUA	Quality Control
1.00	31/12/2020	NTUA	Version to be submitted

Executive Summary

D4.6 – "ChildRescue Pilot Evaluation and Lessons Learnt" reports the results of the evaluation period of the project during the first and second piloting phase and derives lessons learnt during the project.

The originally planned **ChildRescue pilot experimentation** was divided into two parts, the first and the second piloting exercises, consisting respectively of: a) simulation/tabletop exercise and b) a field exercise. Due to the Covid-19 pandemic, the introduction of ChildRescue had to be postponed and the second piloting phase was undertaken not on-site, but virtually and complemented by an additional survey on the effects of ChildRescue on work processes after implementing ChildRescue in the participating organisations had taken place.

The first pilot phase was conducted in the premises of each of the **three pilot organisations** and is documented in D4.3. By the time of the exercise, all ChildRescue components were deployed as the integrated ChildRescue platform and were prepared as needed to support the pilot execution, thus corresponding already to a **TRL 7 (system prototype demonstration in operational environment)**.

Technical partners took up the recommendations derived from the piloting exercise and adaptations were consequently implemented before the second piloting phase.

The second pilot phase was characterised by the effects of the Covid-19-pandemic. In the second pilot phase, simulated exercises with the further developed ChildRescue App and platform were carried out and are documented in D4.5. The second pilot phase was conducted during the first semester of 2020, where measures for the protection against the COVID-19 pandemic were still in place in both countries, i.e., Greece and Belgium. As a consequence, the methodology had to be adapted. By the time of the exercise, a further developed version with more functionalities of the integrated ChildRescue platform were prepared as needed to support the pilot execution, thus corresponding already to a **TRL 8 (system complete and qualified)**. Afterwards, taking the system into production for CF and SoC, with the apps being launched for the general public, the end result of the platform is that of a **TRL 9 (actual system proven in operational environment)**.

For both piloting exercises, three scenarios each were provided by the pilot organisations to support the pilot operation; two for the Missing Children Emergency Case (Greece-supported by SoC and Belgium-supported by Child Focus) and one for the Discovery and Identification of Unaccompanied Minors (Greece-supported by REDCROSS). The developed scenarios were based **on true facts** to create a plausible environment, but any personal data related to the children were **carefully anonymised**. Members and staff of the pilot organisations participated in the exercise and were supported by the technical partners of ChildRescue consortium. The execution of the tabletop exercise¹ followed the pilot guidelines provided in D4.2 for the first piloting exercise, respectively in D4.4 for the second piloting exercise.

¹ A tabletop exercise is one of the seven types of exercises identified by the Homeland Security Exercise Evaluation Program for preparing for disasters and implies discussion-based and field-based exercises.

Key findings and lessons learnt

Theoretical concepts contributed to the understanding of different categories of missing children cases. Computational based theories for activity and behaviour analysis contributed a) to identify the most appropriate indicators that could form a basic profile of a missing child case and b) to apply the most appropriate algorithms for data analysis that could offer valuable insights and predictions. However, an impeding factor for establishing Activity profiling to analyse social networks presence of missing children is the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). The challenges of the application of theories on real-world data are reported in D2.5.

An important lesson learnt is that **each child is unique**, and thus cannot be treated based solely on past cases and experiences from other children. The **child's current mindset** can turn a case into an **unpredictable sequence of events**. As a consequence, predicting or classifying a case into a missing child type have to be handled with care as predictive results are the computational products of data correlations which indicate probability and not certainty.

The **development of the ChildRescue App and platform was undertaken in an iterative process** taking into account the results of the evaluations carried out and took into consideration the different circumstances and backgrounds of the three participating practise partner organisations which were located in Belgium (Child Focus) and Greece (SoC, REDCROSS).

The **mixed-methods approach** of focus groups, qualitative and quantitative survey procedures, **enabled strong results for the further development** of the app and platform. Another major factor was the **well-established and direct communication** between developers, pilot and scientific partners. Future research could take up **participatory designs to complement the methodological approach in order to grasp the situation of children before and during their disappearance and achieve deeper insights in order to develop preventative programs which could be taken up by ChildRescue.**

All piloting organisations stressed the **potential to ease workflows and improve upon their existing techniques** by the additional use of ChildRescue. The surveys offered a valuable source to identify further potential for improvement of the app and platform in each state that it was presented to them. **Most important outcome is that all partners have a positive attitude and readiness to use ChildRescue in their everyday work**; ChildRescue already providing sufficient benefits such as improved time scales with respect of informing the public or the time needed for creating complete case reports. Mandatory work processes at the REDCROSS leading to double entries in the documentation seem to be bearable due to the other (data documentation) benefits of ChildRescue.

Most target values of technical KPIs were achieved apart from GDPR restrictions for using social network connectors and legacy systems, and lack of open, linked data relevant to the ChildRescue's goals.

Despite the pandemic situation and its adverse effects on travelling and face-to-face meetings, the first public launch took place in July 2020. Outcomes are described in detail in D5.6.

An important lesson learnt was that the **specific organisational context** with its legal requirements, existing tools and workflows have to be taken into account in order to achieve as much as possible out of the potential of ChildRescue. The different pilot organisations differ in their target groups, work processes, technological equipment and legal and other organisational requirements. For the distribution of ChildRescue to new organisations, these aspects have to be taken into account, and specific adaptations seem to be inevitable.

The situation of missing unaccompanied migrant minors is even more complex as it also requires insights in transnational procedures and processes. The merits of ChildRescue are the theoretical-based approach which takes into consideration the different categories of missing children, the continuous exchange with the pilot partners in the development of the app and the platform, the deep insight into the work practise and required adaptations and the continuously evaluated product which proved to have a variety of benefits for the work process, thus contributing for quicker information leading to a quicker finding of missing children.

Public engagement and broad participation of citizens is an ongoing business challenge for ChildRescue. The quantification of the minimum number of users that need to use the ChildRescue application for it to deliver the promised results and work significantly better than existing solutions is a research challenge that ChildRescue is also engaging with and attempts to solve. NTUA developed a simulation environment that could create an easy-to-reconfigure concept of effectiveness for the ChildRescue mobile application, which takes into account the specifics of an area such as geography, mobility etc. Oncoming publications describe the concept in more detail.

Table of Contents

Abbreviations List	10
1 Introduction	11
1.1 Purpose & Scope	11
1.2 Structure of the deliverable	11
1.3 Relation to other WPs & Tasks	12
2 Piloting Review	13
2.1 Pilot Overview	13
2.1.1 Feedback from both pilots for Smile of the Child (SoC)	16
2.1.2 Feedback from both pilots for Child Focus	23
2.1.3 Feedback from both pilots for REDCROSS	28
2.2 Feedback from the additional survey	34
2.2.1 Findings of Participants Feedback	35
2.2.2 ChildRescue KPIs based on Survey	41
2.3 Implementation of the Feedback	43
2.3.1 Technical modification of the App	43
2.3.2 Technical modification of the Platform	44
3 Review of used theoretical concepts	46
3.1 System theories	47
3.2 Victimology	47
3.3 Computational Based Theories for Activity and Behaviour Analysis	48
4 Impact assessment	50
4.1 Technical KPIs	50
4.2 Dissemination	53
4.3 Impact on piloting organisations	53
4.3.1 Impact on workflow in SoC	53
4.3.2 Impact on workflow in Child Focus	54
4.3.3 Impact on workflow in REDCROSS	55
4.4 Challenges and Impact beyond the project	56
5 Planned further exploitation of ChildRescue	59
6 Future Technical Modifications Planning	62
7 Conclusions	64
8 Annex I: References	68

List of Figures

Figure 1-1: Relation of D4.6 to other deliverables and tasks	12
Figure 4-1 The ChildRescue suggested solution for addressing the question on the minimum number of ChildRescue application users needed.	57

List of Tables

Table 2-1: Number of participants and form of data accumulated in the piloting exercises.....	14
Table 2-2: Rating of the accessibility of the mock-up Volunteers mobile app and the first version of the Community app during the First Pilot Phase (SoC).....	17
Table 2-3: Rating of the accessibility of the two differing apps, Volunteers mobile app and the Community app, during the second Pilot Phase (SoC).....	17
Table 2-4: Rating of the accessibility of the Profiling & Action relevant functions of the platform during the first Pilot Phase (SoC).....	18
Table 2-5: Rating of the accessibility of the Profiling, Action, Collaboration & Archiving relevant functions of the platform during the second Pilot Phase (SoC)	19
Table 2-6: Assessment of the usability of ChildRescue during the first Piloting Phase (SoC)	20
Table 2-7: Assessment of the usability of ChildRescue during the second Piloting Phase (SoC)	22
Table 2-8: Rating of the accessibility of the mock-up Volunteers mobile app and the first version of the Community app during the First Pilot Phase (Child Focus).....	23
Table 2-9: Rating of the accessibility of the two differing apps, Volunteers mobile app and the Community app, during the second Pilot Phase (Child Focus).....	24
Table 2-10: Rating of the accessibility of the Profiling & Action relevant functions of the platform during the first Pilot Phase (Child Focus)	24
Table 2-11: Rating of the accessibility of the Profiling, Action, Collaboration & Archiving relevant functions of the platform during the second Pilot Phase (Child Focus)	25
Table 2-12: Assessment of the usability of during the first Pilot Phase of ChildRescue (Child Focus).	26
Table 2-13: Assessment of the usability during the second Pilot Phase of ChildRescue (Child Focus)	27
Table 2-14: Rating of the accessibility of the mock-up Volunteers mobile app and the first version of the Community app during the first Phase (REDCROSS)	29
Table 2-15: Rating of the accessibility of the Volunteers mobile app and the Community app during the second Phase (REDCROSS).....	30
Table 2-166: Rating of the accessibility of the platform with Profiling & Action functionalities during the first Phase (REDCROSS)	31
Table 2-17: Rating of the accessibility of the platform with Profiling, Action, Collaboration & Archiving functionalities during the second Phase (REDCROSS)	32
Table 2-18: Assessment of the usability of ChildRescue during the first piloting Phase (REDCROSS).	33
Table 2-19: Assessment of the usability of ChildRescue during the second piloting phase (REDCROSS)	33
Table 2-20: Rating of the duration of workflows with and without ChildRescue in SoC.....	37

Table 2-21: Rating of the duration of workflows with and without ChildRescue in Child Focus.....	38
Table 2-22: Rating of the length of workflows with and without ChildRescue in REDCROSS	40
Table 2-23 Mobile app updates after the pilots.....	43
Table 2-24 Platform updates after the pilots	44
Table 3-1: Theories selected for the different types of missing children cases.....	47
Table 3-2. List of theories applied in ChildRescue.....	48
Table 4-1 Technical KPIs with reached values	51
Table 6-1: Recommended Modifications for the ChildRescue Solution	63

Abbreviations List

CRM	Customer Relationship Management
Dx.x	Deliverable x.x
EC	European Commission
EKKA	National Centre for Social Solidarity
EU	European Union
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GPS	Global Positioning System
IASC	Inter Agency Standing Committee
ICRC	International Committee of the Red Cross
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
MFC	REDCROSS Multifunctional Center
MCOs	Missing Children Organisations
PBM	Performance Based Management
RFL	Restore Family Links operations by Tracing Department of Redcross
S&R	Search & Rescue
TS	Tracing Service
Tx.x	Task x.x
UMC	Unaccompanied Migrant Children
UNHCR	United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose & Scope

ChildRescue aims at developing a complementary tool to current work practices of organisations searching for missing children by implementing an app and corresponding online platform that promotes social awareness and uses new technological and scientific insights. It involves the creation and evaluation of a mobile application for both Android and iOS users that have been reported on in D4.3 and D4.5, respectively.

This report is the final outcome of T4.6 – "ChildRescue Pilots Evaluation, Lessons Learnt and Impact Assessment" [M36] and contains the documentation and assessment of the evaluation efforts as they were presented in earlier reports. It further contains the feedback from the additional surveys that were put in place to account for the necessary changes due to the Covid-19 outbreak during the second piloting phase. D4.6 hence serves the purpose to discuss the evaluation outcomes throughout the complete piloting phase of the project and weigh the chosen theoretical and methodological frameworks in the light of the feedback from the piloting organisations. Furthermore, methodological adoption guidelines for the utilisation of ChildRescue by the participating piloting organisations or other stakeholders are introduced in the context of this deliverable.

1.2 Structure of the deliverable

This deliverable 4.6 is structured as follows:

Section 2 is dedicated to the discussion of the data gathered during the piloting phase. Therefore, it will be looked at the results from the first and second piloting exercises in order to give an insight in the overall impression of the app and platform during the different development phases. The piloting organisations will further report the factors helping or hindering acceptance of the ChildRescue solution in everyday work practice. The newly introduced additional surveys are analysed to get insights into the efficiency of working with ChildRescue in comparison to the duration of work practices without ChildRescue in order to assess the meeting of benchmarks as set out in the original KPIs. The technical partners then share the modifications they have put in place in reaction to the feedback from the piloting exercises.

Section 3 presents the originally chosen theoretical backbone of ChildRescue in light of the lessons learnt throughout the implementation phase and discusses how they impact on the applicability of ChildRescue in different circumstances of missing children cases.

Section 4 is dedicated to the assessment of the impact of ChildRescue from different perspectives. The meeting of benchmarks in both the technical KPIs as well as the dissemination efforts will be demonstrated along with the impact of ChildRescue on the workflow in each of the three piloting organisations before potential impact beyond the project and the limitations of it are discussed.

Section 5 serves the demonstration of planned future exploitation of ChildRescue by all three piloting partners.

In section 6, the technical partners make recommendations for future technical modifications that may be of importance to ensure that the app and platform remain operational.

1.3 Relation to other WPs & Tasks

D4.6 relates to all former deliverables, in so far as it reflects the lessons learnt throughout the project. It specifically takes the data retrieved for D4.3, D4.4 and D4.5 into account by summarising and combining the results of both piloting phases. Since D4.6 is the final evaluation of the project, the theories used and discussed in D2.1 and D2.5 shall therefore also be analysed in their usefulness for the final product of the project. This re-evaluation of the used theories largely relies on the work already finalised in WP2 but will assess the chosen theories from the standpoint of the needs of the evaluation phase. Due to the necessary changes to the piloting phase caused by the Pandemic-situation, which was presented in D4.5, an additional survey was conducted after the second piloting phase to analyse work flows with ChildRescue once it had been introduced into practice.

Figure 1-1: Relation of D4.6 to other deliverables and tasks

2 Piloting Review

2.1 Pilot Overview

The **ChildRescue pilot experimentation** is divided into two parts, the first and the second piloting exercises, consisting respectively of: a) simulation/tabletop exercise and b) a field exercise. D4.3 documents the first pilot phase conducted in the premises of each of the **three pilot organisations**. By the time of the exercise, and as a consequence of it, all ChildRescue components were deployed as the integrated ChildRescue platform and were prepared as needed to support the pilot execution, thus corresponding already to a **TRL 7 (system prototype demonstration in operational environment)**.

Technical partners took up the recommendations derived from the piloting exercise adaptations were consequently implemented before the second piloting phase.

D4.5 documents the simulated exercises of the second pilot phase with the further developed ChildRescue App and platform. This was conducted during the first semester of 2020 where measures for the protection against the COVID-19 pandemic were still in place in both countries, i.e., Greece and Belgium. As a consequence, the methodology had to be adapted. By the time of the exercise, a further developed version with more functionalities of the integrated ChildRescue platform and were prepared as needed to support the pilot execution, thus corresponding already to a **TRL 8 (system complete and qualified)**.

Since then, ChildRescue was further developed, by the technical partners' own resources, as a product, and the system went into production for CF and SoC, with the apps being launched for the general public. With these developments, the end result of the platform is that of a **TRL 9 (actual system proven in operational environment)**.

For both piloting exercises three scenarios were provided by the pilot organisations to support the pilot operation; two for the Missing Children Emergency Case (Greece-supported by SoC and Belgium-supported by Child Focus) and one for the Discovery and Identification of Unaccompanied Minors (Greece-supported by REDCROSS). The developed scenarios were based **on true facts** to create a plausible environment, but any personal data related to the children were **carefully anonymised**. Members and staff of the pilot organisations participated in the exercise and were supported by the technical partners of ChildRescue consortium. The execution of the tabletop exercise² followed the pilot guidelines provided in D4.2. for the first piloting exercise, respectively in D4.4 for the second piloting exercise.

Following table provides an overview of the number of participants and the different data collection methods:

² A tabletop exercise is one of the seven types of exercises identified by the Homeland Security Exercise Evaluation Program for preparing for disasters and implies discussion-based and field-based exercises.

Table 2-1: Number of participants and form of data accumulated in the piloting exercises

	Form of data collection	Number of participants
1 st piloting exercise – qualitative data	Focus groups of participants	SoC= 13, Child Focus= 9, RED-CROSS= 9
1 st piloting exercise – quantitative data	Surveys of participants	SoC= 13, Child Focus= 9, RED-CROSS= 9
2 nd piloting exercise – qualitative data	Interviews with participating staff members	SoC= 6, Child Focus= 12, RED-CROSS= 2
2 nd piloting exercise – quantitative data	Surveys of participants	SoC= 6, Child Focus= 13, RED-CROSS= 5

In the following the methodological adaptations caused by the Covid-19 Pandemic are described, followed by the description of the setting and results evaluating the different stages of the ChildRescue App and Platform. Chapter 2.1 presents the results with respect to each participating organisation, Chapter 2.2 addresses the results of an additional survey on the effects of the work process, followed by Chapter 2.3 describing the technical implementation of the suggested improvement and amendments.

Methodological Adaptation due to the Covid-19 Pandemic

Originally, the ChildRescue solution was planned to be tested with real cases (field exercise) throughout the second phase of the evaluation. However, the Covid-19 pandemic made it necessary to change the methodological approach due to the required safety measures. The following adaptations were made:

1. The original plan for the second piloting exercise, which included a mock case of a real-life case with volunteers on the street, had to be altered. After the simulations, as the testing with real cases was not possible, ChildRescue was directly put to use in a **real operational environment**. As a consequence, the complexity of learning to utilise ChildRescue was increased for the piloting partners.
2. A **remote training** was established, which lacked the experience of the planned face-to-face testing phase. Remote training in the use of new technological developments such as ChildRescue turned out more difficult to comprehend than a face-to-face training combined with the on-site testing of the app and platform. Participants of the remote training found it demanding to become familiar with the functionalities in digital settings and needed more time than anticipated to get acquainted with ChildRescue.
3. New scenarios based on facts from old cases were drawn up to test the functionalities of the further developed app and platform. Therefore, a **digital survey** of staff members and volunteers as well as interviews with staff members was carried out. This survey focused on new respectively further improved functionalities of the app and the platform. Objectives of the survey were to obtain potential suggestions and indications for improvements.
4. Once, ChildRescue had been implemented in the everyday work of the piloting organisations by mid-October 2020 an **additional short survey** on the frequency of the use of ChildRes-

cue and the duration of workflows when using it was designed and filled out by staff members of the piloting partners. Results are discussed in chapter 2.2 of this deliverable.

Setting of the piloting phases

The piloting exercises were carried out utilising a **mix of methods** in order to obtain a broader insight into the socio-technical system of ChildRescue. **Tabletop exercises** were carried out to obtain an insight in the functionalities of the respective stage of the system; **focus groups** were performed and provided qualitative on the subjective experience of ChildRescue and assumed impact on workflows and work processes; a **questionnaire** was administered to find indicators for functionality and usability of the system and an **additional survey** was carried out on the effects of ChildRescue on work processes at the end of the project.

During the first piloting exercise, the alpha version of the solution (which has already achieved TRL=7), not yet open to the general public but already containing the core defined functionalities was presented to the piloting organisations. The version as it was presented in the first tabletop exercise, already fulfilled all requirements that ChildRescue had set for the end of the project, thereby delivering a TRL 7 early in the evaluation phase. Since then and till the beginning of the second piloting phase, more functions were added, and optimisations were made by the technical partners, based on the feedback received. The focus on the second phase was mostly on the support of the volunteers, considering that the core functionalities of the platform and the App had already been reviewed and were already evaluated positively. These additional functions meant that the solution presented during the second round was already rated at a TRL 8, thereby surpassing the aim that was originally set for ChildRescue. Furthermore, due to the participants being mostly volunteers, they were not as versed in the idea of ChildRescue and therefore had a harder time in rating some of the functionalities. As a consequence, some expected to be presented with a final product and were not aware of the ongoing technical implementation and extension that were taking place. Instead, they rated the presented solution as if it was final, which should be taken into consideration during the interpretation of the data. Most comments and feedback collected during the second piloting exercises were implemented into the ongoing technical development of the app and platform, which further elevated the TRL 8 to a TRL 9 by the end of the project, thereby surpassing the expectations greatly.

The general outcome of the evaluation was that the participants were overall positive towards the ChildRescue solution throughout both piloting phases. As expected, there were some differences in the ranking of the app and platform between the organisations, as each organisation has different systems in place, as well as different procedures and tools that their personnel is already familiar with. It should further be noted that during the two piloting phases, both the participants as well as the form of the product that was presented, varied. Therefore, the comparison of data cannot be undertaken in a direct manner but should rather be understood as an indication for improvement for the ChildRescue solution in its different stages. During the first tabletop exercise, when the alpha version, which consisted of the core functionalities and was already scored at the TRL aim for the overall project, was shown, the intuitive use was naturally higher – since the solution itself was not yet sophisticated. Through the additional improvements and integration of more functions made between the first and second phase, the solution was more complex, as any additional feature complicates the understanding of a technological solution. However, the added features greatly add to the overall value of ChildRescue and were direct implementations of feedback collected from the partici-

pants of the first piloting exercise. In order to address any remaining confusion, a PowerPoint presentation showcasing the functionalities of both the app and the platform and contextualising them with the added benefit for the organisations, has been drafted and is available for new interested organisations as well as the piloting partners through MCE. Furthermore, the expectation of some of the participants to be presented with the final product in the second piloting exercise led to a lower rating of the design, which has since been addressed in later versions of the app.

Throughout the two piloting phases, different numbers of participants, partly with different roles were available for the piloting exercises and, consequently, the evaluation of the exercise itself as well as the showcased functionalities of the app and platform. Due to the small sample size of the evaluation rounds (cf. table 2-1), no generalisability can be claimed for the results. Also, in some of the organisations, the participants varied, with different people in different roles/positions attending the first and second round of the evaluation. This should be taken into consideration as a limitation to the data set, which should, therefore, be considered as showcasing a trend rather than clear results. Furthermore, during the quantitative surveys, participants voiced points of departure for further improvement rather than an evaluation of the presented solution. The feedback was addressed by the technical partners in their implementation of changes after the evaluation rounds (cf. chapter 2.3 of this deliverable). Additionally, the piloting organisations vary greatly in their target groups as well as certain workflows when handling missing children cases. While the REDCROSS mainly works in sheltering unaccompanied minors and therefore specifically targets missing unaccompanied migrant minors through the use of ChildRescue, Child Focus and SoC do not have such a clear-cut subgroup of targeted missing children. While both organisations often handle cases of missing runaways (due to the high statistical frequency of these cases), they also address all other groups of missing children. However, the workflows in handling missing children cases vary between these organisations as well, vastly due to different legal frameworks in the respective countries. The formation and organisation of volunteer search and rescue teams, for example, is a useful feature of ChildRescue that can, however, only be used by SoC, since Child Focus does not utilise search and rescue teams in general. The specific differences in handling missing children cases, therefore, also directly influences the evaluation of certain functionalities, which is why the evaluation of the organisations shall be discussed separately from each other in the following sub-chapters.

2.1.1 Feedback from both pilots for Smile of the Child (SoC)

Throughout all phases of the testing, the main result was that the participants warmly welcomed ChildRescue as an additional tool for their work.

In the following, the results of the utilised form on functionalities and usability are presented in the form of tables. During both piloting phases, the participants were asked to rank the accessibility and usability of the app in the form that it was presented to them at that point, on a scale from 1-5 ("1= Very bad"; "2= Bad"; "3= ok", 4= Ok" and "5= Very good"). Items which were rated the same by all three organisations in the respective exercise have been underlined. Additionally, items that were rated by half or less of the participants were highlighted in yellow. The mean was taken as a measure for the description of results. Mean is a measurement for univariate distributions which halves a measurement series according to its size. As a measure for dispersion, the average deviation was taken. All results are tentative results because of the factors mentioned above such as lack of continuity of persons throughout all piloting tests, varying numbers of participants, different roles of participants in the work processes and different versions of the ChildRescue app.

The following table gives an indication of the accessibility regarding the mock-up Volunteers mobile app and the first version of the Community app during the first Pilot Phase.

Table 2-2: Rating of the accessibility of the mock-up Volunteers mobile app and the first version of the Community app during the First Pilot Phase (SoC)

First piloting phase n=13		
median	ad	Item
5	0,46	Size of text
4	0,42	Features are understandable for staff members
5	0,77	Colour of text
5	0,46	Contrast between text and background
5	0,46	Easy to use
5	0,67	Usability in everyday work
5	0,4	Understandable for volunteers
5	0,2	Protecting sensitive data
4	0,62	Navigation in App
4	0,46	Intuitive use of App
5	0,36	Alarm signals audible

The following table gives an indication of the accessibility of the further developed version with more functionalities for the Volunteers mobile app and the Community app during the second Pilot Phase.

Table 2-3: Rating of the accessibility of the two differing apps, Volunteers mobile app and the Community app, during the second Pilot Phase (SoC)

Second piloting phase n=6		
median	ad	Item
4	0	Size of text
3	0,67	Features are understandable for staff members
4	0,33	Colour of text

4	0,17	Contrast between text and background
3	0,4	Easy to use
3	0,67	Usability in everyday work
3	0,25	Understandable for volunteers
4	0	Protecting sensitive data
3,5	0,5	Navigation in App
2,5	0,58	Intuitive use of App
3	0,67	Alarm signals audible

It has to be noted that in the second piloting exercise, less than half of the participants of the first piloting exercise were involved, which limits the explanatory power.

The following table presents an overview of the accessibility of the Profiling & Action relevant functions of the platform during the first Pilot Phase.

Table 2-4: Rating of the accessibility of the Profiling & Action relevant functions of the platform during the first Pilot Phase (SoC)

First piloting phase n=13		Item
median	ad	
5	0,31	Size of text
5	0,25	Features are understandable for staff members
5	0,31	Colour of text
5	0,46	Contrast between text and background
5	0,54	Easy to use
5	0,62	Usability in everyday work
4	0,43	Understandable for volunteers
5	0,36	Protecting sensitive data
5	0,31	Navigation in Platform
5	0,38	Intuitive use of Platform
4,5	0,88	Alarm signals audible

The assessment of the further developed version of the accessibility of the Profiling, Action, Collaboration & Archiving relevant functions of the platform during the second Pilot Phase is presented below.

Table 2-5: Rating of the accessibility of the Profiling, Action, Collaboration & Archiving relevant functions of the platform during the second Pilot Phase (SoC)

Second piloting phase n=6		
median	ad	Item
4	0,33	Size of text
4	0,4	Features are understandable for staff members
4	0,17	Colour of text
4	0,4	Contrast between text and background
3,5	1	Easy to use
3	0,83	Usability in everyday work
3	0,25	Understandable for volunteers
4	0,2	Protecting sensitive data
3,5	0,83	Navigation in Platform
3	0,33	Intuitive use of Platform
1,5	0,5	Alarm signals audible

In the case of the standardised questionnaire on functionalities and usability, the organisation Smile of the Child (SoC) rated ChildRescue the highest out of all three organisations during the first piloting phase (for details, also review D4.3) which might be contributed to the higher number of participants. During the second pilot phase, less than half, i.e., six persons participated in the evaluation. The focus was on additional (new) functionalities and was performed by new staff members and volunteers who did not participate in the initial training that involved the core functionalities of the platform. Some of the participants expressed their (wrong) view that they were presented with a final product, which led to their confusion in relation to certain aspects of the app and platform. All interviewed participants voiced their positive attitude toward the potential of working with ChildRescue in the future but used the surveys as a means to hint at single points that could be improved upon even further. They specifically pointed out the helpfulness of ChildRescue in enabling direct and faster contact with the public, which further establishes that the premise of ChildRescue works in increasing the efficiency of the search for missing children. The functionalities of the second phase involved the components related to the Action and Collaboration phases of the Investigation cycle. These mainly include the volunteers' management, the collaboration between managers and Search and Rescue teams, the Control room and the assistance provided by the data analytics during the investigation.

The overall evaluation of SoC during the second iteration pilot phase lies somewhere between 'good' and 'ok'. The main reason for this evaluation seems to be the higher expectations of the participants regarding the platform and the mobile apps, which were at the stage of a fully functional prototype, but not yet a complete, bug-free, product. However, another possibility could also be in the attitudes of participants who in general, might tend to lower ratings compared to others.

Regarding the usability of the solution, the participants had to evaluate six factors, as shown in the table below. Due to the delay that was caused by the Covid-19 outbreak, the use and adoption of ChildRescue in the everyday work had not happened at the time. As a result, the usability factors were based on estimations relied on the digital mock-up cases that were presented during the remote exercise and thus are not representative of the operational solution. Through the additional interviews that were held, it also became abundantly clear that participants were mostly unsure about the usability due to their lack of training in using the app and platform as well as their lack of opportunities to employ the solution in their everyday work. However, they were all excited about the potential of ChildRescue to improve the efficiency of their work once they were trained in employing the app and platform.

Yet, it should be noted that **the participants from SoC did establish their willingness to use ChildRescue in their work and expressed an overall positive attitude to the potential of the app and platform during the qualitative interviews of the second piloting exercise.** Furthermore, the promised TRL 7 was already fulfilled in the first piloting phase, therefore, the evaluation of the periods after the first phase represents perspectives on a product that was developed to a high stage, but while it was still being developed, some participants expressed that they were under the (false) impression that they were rating the final product.

Table 2-6: Assessment of the usability of ChildRescue during the first Piloting Phase (SoC)

First piloting phase n=13		Item
median	ad	
4	0,44	Organising volunteers
3,5	1	Recruiting new volunteers
5	0,5	Timely response to missing cases
5	0,55	Increasing the speed of recovery of missing children
5	0,6	Matching old similar cases to new cases
5	0,5	Establishing relevant locations of missing children

Regarding pilot phase I, during the first tabletop exercise, the key personnel of SoC had the opportunity to familiarise with the ChildRescue platform, use its value-adding features and experience how

ChildRescue can be integrated into the organisation's existing procedures. Furthermore, the participants provided invaluable feedback on the implemented mobile and web application. The execution of the pilot exercise served another purpose: testing the platform in a controlled environment that simulates real-life situations.

The technical partners conducted a one-day seminar (face to face) during the tabletop exercise in order to train staff members of SoC about the main steps that the actors should follow when using the ChildRescue platform.

One main outcome was that the information coming from the citizens has to be carefully evaluated and keep any potential evidence as probable. Only when the child is located, one can be sure about the credibility of the provided evidence. It was suggested that the terms Point Last Seen (PLS) and Last Known Position (LKP) should be differentiated. Suggested modifications and changes were proposed to the technical partners, as presented thoroughly in D4.3.

Among the challenges, the following were identified and addressed (cf. D 4.3):

- The work of the Network Manager can be highly assisted by the availability for free of a Position tracking system of the volunteers during the search and rescue actions
- For profiling that can also assist the search and rescue teams, other material can also be taken into account such as the "Missing Person Behaviour Handbook or the Lost person behaviour handbook".
- Profiling for the cases of abductions cannot be applied
- Due to the GDPR restrictions, only public data from social accounts can be examined; however, the authorities always have the option to request a break of confidentiality constraints for missing children in danger

The participants agreed that they would use the ChildRescue platform in their work and also work toward widespread use of the app through the public in Greece since they flagged a **number of distinct advantages of working with the ChildRescue tools**. These are the possibility to quickly create alerts, communicate within the search team and extract case reports, relate the current case to potential earlier instances of the child going missing and the outcome of these cases. Also, increased data protection for the child was identified as a benefit, since the dissemination of alerts through media channels or social media leaves a higher risk of the alerts not being deleted in a timely fashion or even at all. Additionally, feedback from the users can be evaluated in order to identify unreliable or irrelevant information (for example, so-called 'trolls') easier. The public, in turn, benefits by being able to quickly provide information without having to know the hotline number and to include videos or photos for better identification. Additionally, they have the possibility to follow cases in their area, which can serve as an incentive to engage more actively with missing children cases. Lastly, the missing children themselves can profit from the faster recovery, as the risk of victimisation for the missing children rises with the time they are unsupervised.

Pilot phase II included the field exercise where the second release of the platform/app was tested, mainly focusing on the functionalities for volunteers. During the first day, a half-day seminar was conducted by representatives of the technical partners (via the Webex platform) that included the main steps that each actor should follow. Functionalities of the app were also presented with a PPT presentation. For the field exercise, some participants were gathered at the premises of the organisation, simulating the Operational Centre of the Organisation and the European helpline for missing children 116000, while the majority of the players were at the places they had declared before the

exercise, as these places were used for simulating the virtual movement of the missing child during the exercise.

Following table presents the assessment of the usability of ChildRescue during the second piloting exercise.

Table 2-7: Assessment of the usability of ChildRescue during the second Piloting Phase (SoC)

Second piloting phase n=6		Item
median	ad	
3	0,6	Organising volunteers
3	0,25	Recruiting new volunteers
3	0,25	Timely response to missing cases
4	0,33	Increasing the speed of recovery of missing children
/		Matching old similar cases to new cases
3	0,6	Establishing relevant locations of missing children

Apart from the challenges mentioned after pilot phase I, few additional challenges can be included such as the usefulness, in the cases of missing children in urban environments, to mark the areas of search (maps) not using radius but using blocks.

The results of those staff members that participated in the field exercise showed a generally positive attitude towards ChildRescue, but also differing views on the helpfulness of it in its presented state. However, this is greatly attributed to the fact that members of the Search and Rescue team, who are already using specific software applications for this cause, seemed to have higher expectations regarding the services for the management of different groups of volunteers and the communication among them that were not fully met, even though it was explicitly explained that ChildRescue is not meant to be a replacement of their current SAR software. Some practical recommendations leading to a higher level of content with ChildRescue were suggested and implemented. Some of the presented actions could not be supported by the iOS version of the mobile app in its current state and the real case management, or field operation needs to be taken into account to increase the innovative character of the ChildRescue solution. Finally, some design issues and user-friendliness of the mobile app (such as accessibility issues concerning colouring and contrast) were raised by the participants.

After the field exercise, specific modifications and proposed changes were submitted to the technical partners, described in detail in D4.5. All the participants expressed the willingness to use the app, endorsing it with increased interest in case the additional features are made available. Participants mentioned the helpfulness of the app in communicating with the public, especially since members of the public will be enticed to help if they realise that the disappearance is in their area.

As an overall assessment by the pilot phases I and II, the participants found the platform and app to be useful for their everyday work. For the operating line (Case Managers), the web platform proved to cover all of their needs, supplementing their existing processes. The Network Manager and the Search and Rescue Team found both the platform and the app to be of assistance in their work, but only with the simultaneous use of other tools that the team already employs. Further technical improvements were suggested to maximise the benefits for a) the organisation, b) the citizens and c) the missing children.

2.1.2 Feedback from both pilots for Child Focus

The main result throughout both piloting evaluations was the positive attitude of all participants in using ChildRescue in their work. The first piloting exercise of Child Focus also produced positive results regarding the core functionalities presented. While some individual points were marked lower during the second piloting phase, the interpretation of the quantitative data alongside the qualitative data clearly shows that this should be understood as pointing out aspects for further improvement rather than a dislike for the solution. **All qualitative interviews show an overwhelmingly positive attitude toward ChildRescue as well as a readiness to use the solution in their everyday work.** In the second exercise, the participants (almost the same group of users in this case) were called to evaluate the Action and Collaboration functionality through the execution of their scenario. A difference from SoC that should be highlighted here is that Child Focus uses volunteers mainly to drop leaflets and put up posters around the city, so no search and rescue teams are involved. Thus, the main usage of the collaboration functionality for Child Focus is for task assignment and monitoring of their execution.

The following table provides insight into the assessment of the mock-up Volunteers mobile app and the first version of the Community app.

Table 2-8: Rating of the accessibility of the mock-up Volunteers mobile app and the first version of the Community app during the First Pilot Phase (Child Focus)

First piloting phase n= 9		
median	ad	Item
4	0,33	Size of text
4	0,33	Features are understandable for staff members
4	0,33	Colour of text
4	0,22	Contrast between text and background
4	0,44	Easy to use
4	0,22	Usability in everyday work
4	0,4	Understandable for volunteers
3,5	0,5	Protecting sensitive data

4	0,33	Navigation in App
4	0,22	Intuitive use of App
4	0,25	Alarm signals audible

The table below shows how the further developed Volunteers mobile app and the Community app have been assessed in the second phase.

Table 2-9: Rating of the accessibility of the two differing apps, Volunteers mobile app and the Community app, during the second Pilot Phase (Child Focus)

Second piloting phase n= 13			Item
median	ad		
4	0,31		Size of text
4	0,15		Features are understandable for staff members
4	1		Colour of text
4	0,69		Contrast between text and background
4	0,38		Easy to use
4	0,4		Usability in everyday work
3	0,33		Understandable for volunteers
3	0,43		Protecting sensitive data
4	0,33		Navigation in App
4	0,62		Intuitive use of App
4	0,56		Alarm signals audible

The rating of the accessibility of the Profiling & Action relevant functions of the platform during the first Pilot Phase is presented in the table below.

Table 2-10: Rating of the accessibility of the Profiling & Action relevant functions of the platform during the first Pilot Phase (Child Focus)

First piloting phase n=9			Item
median	ad		

4	0,22	Size of text
4	0,33	Features are understandable for staff members
4	0,44	Colour of text
4	0,11	Contrast between text and background
4	0,22	Easy to use
4	0,25	Usability in everyday work
4	0,33	Understandable for volunteers
3,5	0,5	Protecting sensitive data
4	0,22	Navigation in Platform
4	0,44	Intuitive use of Platform
4	0,33	Alarm signals audible

The results of the further developed version are provided in the table below.

Table 2-11: Rating of the accessibility of the Profiling, Action, Collaboration & Archiving relevant functions of the platform during the second Pilot Phase (Child Focus)

Second piloting phase n=13		Item
median	ad	
4	0,31	Size of text
4	0,17	Features are understandable for staff members
4	0,55	Colour of text
4	0,42	Contrast between text and background
4	0,5	Easy to use
4	0,54	Usability in everyday work
3	0,33	Understandable for volunteers
4	0,71	Protecting sensitive data
4	0,45	Navigation in Platform

4	0,45	Intuitive use of Platform
		Alarm signals audible

The rating of the usability in the case of Child Focus is also based on estimations since ChildRescue had not yet been adopted in their everyday operations. Therefore, the values presented in the following table derive solely from the review of a mock case execution as part of a hypothetical scenario (which was based on a real case). However, recruiting volunteers was not a part of the mock case for the second piloting exercise, which means that the participants from that phase were not shown that specific function and therefore may have felt like they could not judge its functionality. Additionally, Child Focus does not match old cases to new cases in their work practice, which is why half or more of the participants could not estimate the usefulness of ChildRescue for it at all and the other participants gave a 'gut instinct' estimation that is not based on real-life experience and has, therefore, been disregarded.

Table 2-12: Assessment of the usability of during the first Pilot Phase of ChildRescue (Child Focus)

First piloting phase n=9		Item
median	ad	
3	0	Organising volunteers
2,5	0,5	Recruiting new volunteers
4	0,56	Timely response to missing cases
4	0,67	Increasing the speed of recovery of missing children
4	0,67	Matching old similar cases to new cases
4	0,56	Establishing relevant locations of missing children

The table below gives an insight into the assessment of the usability during the second Pilot Phase of ChildRescue.

Table 2-13: Assessment of the usability during the second Pilot Phase of ChildRescue (Child Focus)

Second piloting phase n=13		Item
median	ad	
4	0,75	Organising volunteers
/		Recruiting new volunteers
4	0,1	Timely response to missing cases
4	0,23	Increasing the speed of recovery of missing children
3	0,17	Matching old similar cases to new cases
4	0,33	Establishing relevant locations of missing children

Both pilot exercises were very warmly welcomed by the Child Focus staff. In the first tabletop exercise, the full operational team of Child Focus (who deal with the cases of missing children on a daily basis) was presented, together with the project coordinator and the policy advisor specialised in missing children, responsible for streamlining their external but also internal policies and procedures. In the second pilot, the field exercise, the Network team (responsible for working with the volunteers) was added to this group as at that point also the collaborative working space features for volunteers were tested. Even though there was still room for improvements, the possibilities to organise the volunteers were much appreciated, which reflects the overall feeling in the Network team after the pilot: a good appreciation of the potential of ChildRescue to become a definite added value in streamlining Child Focus's work with the volunteers in the near and slightly further future.

Besides the volunteer section, the following features were thoroughly tested during both pilots:

- Creation of missing children's cases
- Launching of alerts
- Receiving and evaluating information coming in from users in the general public
- Retrieving this information from the platform to be able to send the information to the competent police services dealing with the case
- Changing the range of the alert or add a second alert in a different area
- The control-tab of the platform to get a quick overview of the information inputted and provided in this particular case

For all of these functionalities, the enthusiasm of the team was high and the motivation to start using the platform and application, after improvement of the issues raised, was definitely present. As their operational colleagues, at that point, had a few minutes to get acquainted with the platform, the main concern after the pilots was the rise in workload for the case managers dealing with the case. However important, this is to be put into perspective, as the two pilots were a combination of presentation of the functionalities and testing to give feedback for improvement. As it is usually the case

with (technological) innovations, it takes time to get familiar with these and to gain an in-depth understanding of the functionalities and their added value compared to the existing daily practice. Secondly, although ChildRescue is highly embedded in Child Focus existing procedures, merging of these procedures is still necessary in order to integrate ChildRescue. Coordinating a case of a missing child and especially launching alerts and collecting information from the general public is complicated machinery at Child Focus, with many colleagues from different teams involved. After the pilots, a discussion could start about the integration of ChildRescue into this machinery tackling issues such as: who will play which role of the platform, who will be responsible for what and how will this be coordinated. These questions could not had yet been answered at the moment of the second pilot, which also explains the worry of an increased workload.

As a conclusion, it can be stated that most of the participants assessed ChildRescue as having a large potential to become a true added value in Child Focus daily reality of looking for missing children. Yet, the results of the pilot exercises could not show this full potential in practice, since it was based on a virtual scenario. All participants, however, remained very positive and excited for the near future.

2.1.3 Feedback from both pilots for REDCROSS

The main result throughout both piloting evaluations was the positive attitude of all participants in using ChildRescue in their work. The results from the Hellenic Red Cross (REDCROSS) show a positive attitude towards ChildRescue in both instalments (cf. following tables). During the first iteration, where the core functionality was evaluated, the average for both the platform and the Community app was very close to 4 ('good'). During the second phase, where the Action and Collaboration functionalities of ChildRescue were presented and the complexity increased, the average of the accessibility was closer to 'ok', again for both the platform and the mobile apps. However, as already stated, the quantitative data can only sensibly be interpreted in the context of the qualitative interviews, which showed a positive outlook on ChildRescue, albeit mixed with some worries about the compatibility to workflows that are directed by REDCROSS and have to adhere to strict protocols, thereby possibly making some features less useable for this specific partner. However, the overall basic functions of ChildRescue were welcomed as an additional tool for increasing the efficiency of the work in the organisation.

The rating of the accessibility of the mock-up Volunteers mobile app and the first version of the Community app during the first Piloting Phase can be taken from the table below. Nine participants rated the first product.

Table 2-14: Rating of the accessibility of the mock-up Volunteers mobile app and the first version of the Community app during the first Phase (REDCROSS)

first piloting phase n=9		
median	ad	Item
4	0,78	Size of text
<u>4</u>	<u>0,67</u>	Features are understandable for staff members
4	0,56	Colour of text
4	0,78	Contrast between text and background
4	0,33	Easy to use
4	0,44	Usability in everyday work
4	0,33	Understandable for volunteers
4	0,89	Protecting sensitive data
<u>4</u>	<u>0,5</u>	Navigation in App
3,5	0,88	Intuitive use of App
4	0,57	Alarm signals audible

Results from the assessment of the further developed product are presented in the table below. During the second phase, only five persons participated in the evaluation.

Table 2-15: Rating of the accessibility of the Volunteers mobile app and the Community app during the second Phase (REDCROSS)

second piloting phase		
median	ad	Item
3	0,2	Size of text
4	0	Features are understandable for staff members
3	0	Colour of text
3	0,4	Contrast between text and background
4	0,2	Easy to use
3	0,6	Usability in everyday work
3	0,4	Understandable for volunteers
4	0,4	Protecting sensitive data
3	0	Navigation in App
3	0,25	Intuitive use of App
3	0,4	Alarm signals audible

The table below gives an impression of the Rating of the accessibility of the platform with the Profiling & Action functionalities during the first Piloting phase.

Table 2-166: Rating of the accessibility of the platform with Profiling & Action functionalities during the first Phase (REDCROSS)

First piloting phase n=9		Item
median	ad	
3,5	0,75	Size of text
3,5	0,75	Features are understandable for staff members
4	0,63	Colour of text
4	0,88	Contrast between text and background
4	0,13	Easy to use
4	0,38	Usability in everyday work
4	<u>0,57</u>	Understandable for volunteers
3	0,89	Protecting sensitive data
4	0,38	Navigation in Platform
4	0,5	Intuitive use of Platform
4	0,43	Alarm signals audible

The rating of the further developed product is presented in the table below.

Table 2-17: Rating of the accessibility of the platform with Profiling, Action, Collaboration & Archiving functionalities during the second Phase (REDCROSS)

Second piloting phase n=5		Item
median	ad	
3	0	Size of text
4	0	Features are understandable for staff members
3	0	Colour of text
3	0	Contrast between text and background
4	0,4	Easy to use
3	0,6	Usability in everyday work
3	0,4	Understandable for volunteers
3	0,6	Protecting sensitive data
4	0,2	Navigation in Platform
3	0	Intuitive use of Platform
3	0	Alarm signals audible

As in the previous pilots, the usability evaluation for REDCROSS came as part of the exercise on a mock case scenario and not based on real operation. The outcome shows a stable attitude towards the usability of ChildRescue in everyday operations and the appreciation of the solution in all of the areas examined. The table below presents the results of the nine participants rating the usability during the first Piloting Phase.

Table 2-18: Assessment of the usability of ChildRescue during the first piloting Phase (REDCROSS)

First piloting phase n=9		Item
median	ad	
3	0,5	Organising volunteers
3	0,56	Recruiting new volunteers
3	0,57	Timely response to missing cases
3	0,5	Increasing the speed of recovery of missing children
3,5	0,63	Matching old similar cases to new cases
3	0,5	Establishing relevant locations of missing children

The rating of the second piloting phase is shown in the following table.

Table 2-19: Assessment of the usability of ChildRescue during the second piloting phase (REDCROSS)

Second piloting phase n=5		Item
median	ad	
4	0,33	Organising volunteers
4	0	Recruiting new volunteers
4	0,2	Timely response to missing cases
3	0	Increasing the speed of recovery of missing children
3	0,2	Matching old similar cases to new cases
3	0	Establishing relevant locations of missing children

The overall experience from both piloting exercises was positive with good potentials for future use under certain conditions.

The field exercise specifically provided a good opportunity to better understand how the ChildRescue app and platform can contribute to the REDCROSS procedures, also considering the specificities of the REDCROSS participation in the project. In this regard, the following aspects were tested and evaluated:

- Registration of UMC
- Creation of a list of UMC with each facility/accommodation centre which can potentially be linked with each other to enable a full overview of the UMC supported by the REDCROSS

- The use of the above-mentioned list as a tool to take the presence of the UMC within a REDCROSS facility at different times within a day
- A tool to detect on time possible absences on facility level that can by its turn enable quicker detection of missing children cases and alerts
- Capacity to detect missing children in case of emergencies
- Facilitation of volunteer deployment and update, as well as a research procedure in an emergency situation
- Coordination of different REDCROSS Services, especially when research is needed (including on time-sharing of accurate information at different levels)
- Feeding the ChildRescue with information
- Possibility/ability to serve parallel research of missing children
- Overview of the research procedure – real-time feedback on a map

As an overall outcome, it can be said that both piloting exercises were greatly appreciated by all attendants, who stated that they could see the applicability and the effectiveness of the ChildRescue solution in real-time. This is expected to have a positive impact on the deployment of volunteers, especially in the case of an investigation (at least when a single person goes missing).

There were some concerns expressed by participants on whether the use of the ChildRescue platform would result in doubling the work of involved staff, taking into consideration that there are already a number of databases available with the REDCROSS that should be updated. However, despite the fact that these databases could be connected to ChildRescue, REDCROSS decided against it early on (mainly due to data protection-related issues that had to be solved by the organisation), and therefore these concerns were not considered as valid from the perspective of evaluating the outcomes of ChildRescue.

Similarly, there were also some concerns raised with regard to having access to confidential information collected from the REDCROSS about a UMC to unauthorised personnel, i.e., users of the platform. Such concerns are related to data protection and ownership of the available information, underlining that the REDCROSS environment within the ChildRescue platform should be secured to ensure that the private information of the UMC should be protected and the do no Harm principle would be fully respected. Nevertheless, as the technical partners reassured the participants, this is the case with ChildRescue, where access is provided only to authorised users, and as a result, these concerns are invalid.

Last but not least, it has been highlighted as a useful continuation point that, especially when it comes to UMC, research should not end with their discovery, and that the ChildRescue initiative should be accompanied with a protection follow-up mechanism that will ensure the best interest of the UMC and after it is traced.

2.2 Feedback from the additional survey

In order to gather feedback on the functionality of ChildRescue, three surveys with a variety of items have been conducted. One took place during the first and two during the second piloting phase. They focussed on the duration of different workflows and other parameters. The first two surveys asked, "How would you rate the following (items) **without** the use of the ChildRescue App/Platform". An additional survey has been undertaken in mid-October to ensure all the piloting partners had already

implemented the app and platform in their work and could therefore judge the effect it might have. Here the request was "How would you estimate the following **with** the use of the ChildRescue App/Platform".

Due to the fact that more than half of the participants in all of the organisations could not answer the 'number of investigation activities in irrelevant locations' during the first piloting phase, this item was not analysed and deleted for the remaining two surveys. The high amount of yellow highlighted items (hence, items that were answered by half or less of the participants) in the first surveys from Child Focus and SoC indicated a general uncertainty about the time frames due to the stark difference between cases and roles within the organisation. Therefore, during the second and the additional instalment of the surveys, the estimation-nature of the answers was stressed to reassure participants who were unsure about filling in the surveys without concrete data.

2.2.1 Findings of Participants Feedback

Looking at the tables, the figures seem to be scattered, although the expectation was that the two ratings without the use of the ChildRescue app/platform would be roughly similar. This hardly applies everywhere. An explanation could be that the first survey took place before the Covid-19 lockdown; the second and third survey were carried out during the pandemic situation. Thus, it could be that work processes were changed to meet up requirements assigned to that situation.

Due to the different operational procedures in the different organisations, some questions could not be answered by all the organisations. Child Focus, for example, does not employ search and rescue teams in their work, therefore leading to no answer for the length of gathering such a team with ChildRescue. There is a general trend in all three piloting organisations of varying indications even throughout the two phases when asked about their processes "without the use of ChildRescue" – which should, in theory, be identical – as a lot of the answers are based on estimations rather than actual time measurement. Furthermore, the participants of the first and second piloting exercise were not all identical. They held different roles within the organisations, which may have added to the variations in the answers given. Additionally, the answers for work processes with the use of ChildRescue should be considered an indicator rather than a hard fact, since the participants do not measure the time needed for their workflows when handling missing children cases. Also, the sample sizes were relatively small in nature and varied greatly throughout the different piloting phases, with only staff members who had already used ChildRescue in their work participating in the additional survey.

Yet, the surveys show a trend that can be analysed cautiously despite the listed limitations to the sample and the data set. Additionally, it should be remarked that ChildRescue has been used by the piloting partners as it was originally intended, namely as an additional tool. Therefore, the successful resolution of cases where ChildRescue was applied cannot be accredited exclusively to the use of ChildRescue, since other measures were also used. The implementation of ChildRescue should be seen – fully in accordance to the core concept and project prospects – as an offering increasing the chances of a successful recovery of the missing children rather than an exclusive solution to the cases. The data from the surveys from the different piloting partners moreover show that there are great variations in the estimated timeframes of the organisations, which may be caused by the different procedures in the organisations. Therefore, the surveys from each piloting partner will be discussed separately.

Smile of the Child (Soc)

The table below gives an overview of the estimated duration of different workflows without and with the utilisation of ChildRescue.

The categories which participants could tick for both questions "*How would you rate the following (items) **without** the use of the ChildRescue App/Platform*" and "*How would you estimate the following **with** the use of the ChildRescue App/Platform*" were following numbers 0-1; 2-5; 6-10; 11-15 and 16 or more; don't know and not applicable. To calculate an estimated average, the following average number was taken:

0-0,5 → 0,5;

2-5 → 3,5;

6-10 → 8;

11-15 → 13 and

16 and more → 20,

although the last category will certainly be higher as few children will be missing either a longer period or never be found.

The table below gives an overview of the estimated time needed, except item 4, which refers to the old cases matched to current cases.

In order to interpret the results of the table two clarifications are needed:

Metric 1 in this case **does not take into account the participation of citizens and the provision of facts**, so actually it refers to the time spent from the scope of the case managers of the response organisation (which is estimated that it will be marginally increased), considering that there will be no evidence provided by the citizens for the missing child cases which in this case is expected to make a clear difference.

Similarly, **Metric 2** refers to the time spent **from the person who operates the system** for supporting the formation of the rescue teams; however it **does not include the time spent by the different team leaders of the rescue teams for actually forming the teams**. The figures are not comparable as they refer to a totally different process/ model. The phone-based distributed model for communicating with all the rescue team members (which requires less effort for the manager but much more effort and actual time spent for the team leaders for contacting each team member) has been replaced with a centralised model allowing the formation of form teams without each team leader to have to individually contact all the team members (thus this time is not measured in the first model). Although for both cases the participants of the survey have provided estimations from their point of view, there is no meaning to compare the values between these different models of operation.

Metrics' Description		Without ChildRescue	Without ChildRescue	With ChildRescue
		1. Phase: (n=13) Estimated Average	2. Phase (n=6) Estimated Average	Oct. 2020 (n=6) Estimated Average
1.	average time between reporting of disappearance and locating the missing child	Ø 7,25 hrs	Ø 7,92 hrs	Ø 8,00 hrs
2.	average time needed for volunteer/search & rescue team formation per case	Ø 3,14 hrs	Ø 13,67 hrs	Ø 6,20 hrs
3.	average time needed for citizens to get informed for a case for the first time, after the decision for dissemination	Ø 5,94 hrs	Ø 7,00 hrs	Ø 3,00 hrs
4.	average number of old cases matched to current case	Ø 1,75 cases	Ø 9,00 cases	Ø 8,00 cases
5.	average time needed for examining & retrieving information from old cases similar to current case	Ø 1,75 hrs	Ø 7,00 hrs	Ø 9,00 hrs
6.	average time needed for creating complete case reports	Ø 2,33 hrs	Ø 10,75 hrs	Ø 0,5 hrs

Table 2-20: Rating of the duration of workflows with and without ChildRescue in SoC

The numbers throughout the different phases scatter a lot. Insofar, all the interpretation has to be perceived with sufficient caution. The aforementioned indicators, which have to do with measuring the time needed for achieving a target, are not based on factual results due to the fact that the Covid-19 outbreak did not actually allow to use the app during the pilots in full scale by engaging citizens. So the estimated times refer to administrative time spent by the case managers operating the system but not to actual average times (e.g. for locating the missing child) with the participation of citizens which actually is the most crucial factor based on the core concept and expected value of ChildRescue.

Nevertheless, by examining the results of the internal survey, two items showed a clear improvement in efficiency with the use of ChildRescue, namely the average time needed for citizens to get informed for a case for the first time case; dropping down nearly 50% and the time needed to create complete case reports, which dropped to down to (nearly) 20%. This indicates that ChildRescue can contribute to reduce time efforts – and therefore increase productivity – without much training in the use of it by speeding up the needed evidence on the case development for the reports. Additionally, the use of ChildRescue to recruit social sensors in the wider public serves to increase the speed of informing citizens of a missing child. Also, the numbers of old cases that could be matched to the new case will increase through the use of ChildRescue.

Regarding all the other indicators, the lack of factual results due to the Covid-19 outbreak has focused the evaluation on the administrative effort and time spent but not on justified time estimations of the results on the field, since it was not possible to fully integrate the platform and the App in the operational environment of the organisation, train the personnel as needed and run a long-lasting exercise with real cases that would allow us to collect real results for the analysis. In addition, five of the surveyed staff members from SoC further indicated that they used ChildRescue 1-3 times a month

up until the survey (with the remaining participant indicating use of 1-4 times a week), meaning they have used it in few instances to draw far-reaching conclusions.

Child Focus

The survey results from Child Focus show a similar discrepancy between the two surveys that both indicated the duration of work processes without the use of ChildRescue, thereby underlining the difficulty of the staff members to estimate the duration of different steps in locating missing children (cf. Table 2-11).

Table 2-21: Rating of the duration of workflows with and without ChildRescue in Child Focus

Metrics' Description		Without ChildRescue	Without ChildRescue	With ChildRescue
		1. Phase: (n=13) Estimated Average	2. Phase (n=10) Estimated Average	Oct. 2020 (n=9) Estimated Average
1.	average time between reporting of disappearance and locating the missing child	Ø 20,00 hrs	Ø 18,00 hrs	Ø 17,00 hrs
2.	average time needed for volunteer/search & rescue team formation per case	n/a	n/a	n/a
3.	average time needed for citizens to get informed for a case for the first time, after the decision for dissemination	Ø 6,31 hrs	Ø 4,63 hrs	Ø 1,50 hrs
4.	average number of old cases matched to current case	Ø 0,5 cases	Ø 8,50 cases	Ø 5,75 cases
5.	average time needed for examining & retrieving information from old cases similar to current case	Ø 0,5 hrs	Ø 2,00 hrs	Ø 4,44 hrs
6.	average time needed for creating complete case reports	Ø 2,81 hrs	Ø 1,36 hrs	Ø 0,5 hrs

Participants of the Child Focus surveys struggled especially during the first phase, resulting in a high amount of items that were answered by only half or less of the nine participants, with only two items being filled in by more than half. This effect was dampened by reassuring the participants that the surveys were about subjective estimations during the second phase, which resulted in the items all being answered by more than half of the 13 participants. The item "average time needed for the formation of search and rescue teams" was not analysed, because Child Focus does not employ search and rescue teams in their work process and consequently, is not using this feature of the app.

Compared to the SoC surveys, Child Focus participants showed consistency in some estimations, such as the average time between the reporting and location of a missing child, here mainly '16 or more hrs' were mostly ticked during all three periods. Since this was the highest possible answer, the improvements with ChildRescue might not be traced through these answers.

The majority of cases dealt with at Child Focus remain open more than two days before the child was found, the ambition of getting this answer to more participants estimating it to be below 16 hours seems merely impossible. ChildRescue could impossibly shorten the time to that extent, as the time needed to find the child is linked to many different factors, some of them surpassing the zone of con-

trol of ChildRescue. The Child Focus case managers estimate that ChildRescue can definitely help them shorten this time period (as for instance it dramatically shortens the time needed to launch an alert / public appeal), but not to the extent of getting it to less than 16 hours on average.

The time needed to create complete case reports improved from 2,81 hours to minimum of "0,5" hours, that is all responding participants ticked '0-1 hr' hours average time, indicating a very efficient work process even before the use of ChildRescue that could still be improved with its use.

In addition to these items the average time needed for the citizens to be informed of a new case could be reduced from an 6,21 hrs down to 1,5 hrs in the additional survey. Therefore, the ability to quickly distribute information on cases of missing children, which is crucial for their positive resolution, was estimated to improve more than 4 hours, which is a significant improvement.

The estimated numbers on the average number of old cases that could be matched to the new case are scattered. In the 1st survey, all participants ticked "0-1"; the increase in the 2nd phase without the use of ChildRescue is due to two participants ticking "16 and more", whereas the remaining participants chose "0-1" and "2-5" cases. In the additional survey nobody chose "0-1", but evenly "2-5" and "6-10" cases, two participants did not know. These figures could be explained by the fact that even after the pilots and during the real case testing, it is one of the features that has not yet been heavily used since not a lot of cases are inputted. The matching of the new with older cases is not yet integrated in-depth in the daily practice of the case managers using the platform and the metric provided for this functionality cannot be matched to the prior situation, and in the past, new and old cases were not matched.

Two-thirds of the nine participants indicated that they used ChildRescue 1-3 times a month, with the other three indicating somewhat higher uses of 1-4 times a week. When analysing the surveys on an individual level, it becomes clear that the participants who indicated a more frequent use show a trend to evaluate the items slightly better for the time needed with ChildRescue. This indicates that some of the evaluations might improve once the staff members had a chance to fully implement ChildRescue in their work and therefore familiarise themselves with it. It can hence be deducted, that the initial introduction phase that the participants were largely still in, consequently negatively impacted the overall ratings in all organisations.

REDCROSS

The estimated time frames in the REDCROSS samples were generally higher than the other two pilot-ing organisations, which is due to the different target group and further showed the difficulties in handling cases of missing unaccompanied migrant minors that have been addressed in several academic presentations and publications of ChildRescue (also cf. section 4.4 for more information).

Table 2-22: Rating of the length of workflows with and without ChildRescue in RED-CROSS

Metrics' Description		Without ChildRescue	Without ChildRescue	With ChildRescue
		1. Phase: (n=9) Estimated Average	2. Phase (n=5) Estimated Average	Oct. 2020 (n=7) Estimated Average
1.	average time between reporting of disappearance and locating the missing child	Ø 16,10 hrs	Ø 11,75 hrs	Ø 6,50 hrs
2.	average time needed for volunteer/search & rescue team formation per case	Ø 8,50 hrs	Ø 2,75 hrs	Ø 3,29 hrs
3.	average time needed for citizens to get informed for a case for the first time, after the decision for dissemination	Ø 14,29 hrs	Ø 16,50 hrs	Ø 8,70 hrs
4.	average number of old cases matched to current case	Ø 4,1 cases	Ø 3,8 cases	Ø 13,67 cases
5.	average time needed for examining & retrieving information from old cases similar to current case	Ø 4,25 hrs	Ø 3,5 hrs	Ø 16,00 hrs
6.	average time needed for creating complete case reports	Ø 5,50 hrs	Ø 8,13 hrs	Ø 14,30 hrs

However, the additional surveys also highlight the greater potential impact of ChildRescue on the workflows in this specific subgroup of missing children with four of the six items showing improvement (cf. Table 2–22). Most importantly, the estimated average time between the reporting of the disappearance and the location of missing children has been cut down by nearly 60% from the first survey which is a substantial improvement of the timeframe.

The average time for the formation of search and rescue teams has improved. Also, the average time needed to inform citizens of new cases has dropped by nearly 40% compared to the 1st survey. Additionally – like in the other two organisations as well – the average number of old cases that could be matched to the current case has risen, with the estimated time needed for that workflow, however, rising as well.

Finally, regarding the estimated time needed for the creation of a complete case, it should be noted that REDCROSS per mandate is obliged to follow specific Red Cross procedures that most of them are common on an international level. In this regard, all ChildRescue activities are complementary to regular Red Cross procedures. For activities like the registration of UMC with REDCROSS facilities, REDCROSS staff engaged with ChildRescue need to follow both the Red Cross procedures and the ChildRescue registration process, which duplicates their work. For the time being, there seems to be no possibility for them to use just the ChildRescue registration. As a result, this metric is not measured as it cannot represent a benefit for an organisation that is required to use per mandate another tool.

On the other hand, for the mobilisation and the follow up of volunteers during an investigation, there was no previous e-tool to compare with, so as a result evaluation of the time interval is by assumption. Finally, regarding tracing for the REDCROSS, as humanitarian tracing differs from police procedures and cases may remain open for a long time, the Red Cross Movement has not an average time interval for the conclusion of a case, to be used as a basis for comparison.

Four of the seven participants indicated that they had so far used ChildRescue 1-3 times a month, with the remaining three participants using it 1-4 times a week. Much like with the surveyed staff members from Child Focus, there was a slightly positive trend in the time estimations and the frequency of the use of ChildRescue, hinting at the increase of the beneficial effect of ChildRescue with an increased use of it.

2.2.2 ChildRescue KPIs based on Survey

The number of missing children real-life cases piloting during the evaluation phase was set at ten, which was already fulfilled before the conduction of the additional surveys in mid-October, with ChildRescue being utilised in 48 cases by the time of the additional surveys. So far, most disappearances in which ChildRescue has been used could be resolved with the child being found in good health. Six cases remain open at the time that this report was compiled, all from Child Focus. This can be explained by the normal duration of missing cases and therefore does not reflect an issue with ChildRescue. Due to the multitude of other measures and tools used in these cases, the success rate cannot be attributed to ChildRescue specifically, but it has thereby shown its potential as an additional tool.

So far, 50 citizens contributions have been entered through the app, all in Child Focus. Therefore, the KPI of over 100 contributions could not be reached. However, this may be due to the fact that REDCROSS has so far only utilised the app to register unaccompanied minors in their shelters, none of which had disappeared, therefore giving no ground for a public appeal and SoC has utilised ChildRescue in 25 missing cases, but the members of public so far prefer to use the phone hotline. The slow change from phoning information into using the app may be due to the fact that the public has not yet gotten used to this new technological tool and therefore prefer to use the phone even if they saw the alert on the app. Furthermore, due to the Covid-19 outbreak, not as many people are roaming the streets anymore. Consequently, sightings and citizens contributions through the app have stayed behind expectations.

It should be clarified though the following, as far as REDCROSS participation in the platform is concerned:

- The REDCROSS participation is distinct and real-life cases to be piloted concern registration of UMC with REDCROSS facilities. Due to Covid-19 situation and also because the initial planning was based on vague assumptions that did not take into consideration the time required to have all green lights and consent needed, registration of real cases was possible only in late November. The number of UMC registered and monitored via ChildRescue is, by December 2020, 19 children from 3 facilities.
- In addition, the REDCROSS participates only with staff and volunteers and does not engage the general public within ChildRescue use.

Due to the fact that none of the piloting organisations could indicate how many investigation activities were conducted in "irrelevant" locations (that is locations where the child never was) and the subsequent deletion of this item from the surveys, no conclusive statement can be made about whether the KPI of reducing unsuccessful missions of search and rescue teams by over 30% was reached.

All three organisations could reduce the time before a collaboration with the public was shown when comparing the estimations of this duration without and with ChildRescue. Child Focus reported an

improvement of 1-4 hours. SoC reported an up to 9 hours. Finally, REDCROSS reported an improvement of at least 11-14 hours, if not more (since they indicated '16 or more hours' during the first phase). Thus, the goal of cutting the needed time in half is successfully achieved. Consequently, the increase of the public awareness can also be deemed successful since the faster informing of the public also leads to a more acute knowledge of the users of ChildRescue and therefore their awareness of cases that they may have otherwise not heard about, especially since the paper flyers that Child Focus usually utilises will not be seen by as many people that stay inside due to the Covid-19 outbreak.

The time reduction achieved when using ChildRescue varied significantly for the different piloting partners. While SoC reported a slight increase in the time needed and Child Focus reported steady high numbers, there was a significant drop in the reported length for REDCROSS. This may be due to the fact that the work processes for missing unaccompanied migrant minors are especially complicated and therefore show the most potential for improvement by introducing a homogenous method such as ChildRescue. Therefore, for the group of missing unaccompanied migrant minors, an improvement can be reported for the time between the report of the disappearance and the recovery with an increase of 9-14 or more hours in comparison to the first surveys and an improvement of 1-8 hours in comparison to the second phase. In cases such as the disappearances of minors, this constitutes a major improvement since especially unaccompanied migrant minors can travel long distances in a short time, therefore increasing the chances of a successful recovery through efficient measures.

The productivity could be increased through the use of ChildRescue as shown by the drop-in time to launch a public appeal (which was 1-4 hrs in the case of Child Focus, for example). Additionally, the possibility to quickly report a sighting through the app increases the productivity, since members of the public, who may not be able to phone in any tips due to being at work or otherwise occupied, are more likely to use a faster function such as the ChildRescue system, therefore increasing the probability of public engagement. This rise in productivity also leads to a reduction in costs in staff hours. Through the digital format of the sightings, the delay of information to the police is also quicker, since a 'copy-paste' approach is possible and replaces the lengthy process of taking notes from a telephone call, drafting a report and sending it to the police.

The TRL level of seven (7), which was declared as the aim for the end of the project in the Grant Agreement, had already been reached for the first piloting exercise. Therefore, ChildRescue has been successful in its aim to deliver a functioning product with a higher TRL than originally planned. The TRL during the second piloting phase was already valued at eight (8), rising to a nine (9) after the implementation of the feedback from the second piloting phase. The performance of ChildRescue at such a high level already during the first piloting exercise led to raised expectations with the participants and a rating of the solution at a higher TRL level. Consequently, some participants expected a fully finished product during the second piloting phase, which was not the aim of that stage and rated the presented solution lower due to their increased expectations (despite the product already performing at a higher technology readiness level than envisioned for the end of the project). However, the quantitative data cannot be sensibly interpreted by itself, but should rather always be considered in the context of the qualitative data that was collected during the same exercises. The qualitative data gathered during the second piloting exercise show an overwhelming positivity toward ChildRescue and its use in the everyday work of the piloting partners. Participants in all organisations agreed that they were happy with using ChildRescue as an additional tool in their search for missing children, even before the technical implementations were put in place that resulted from the feedback gath-

ered during the second piloting phase. The qualitative interviews from the second piloting phase, much like the focus groups during the first piloting exercise, underlined the excitement and positive attitude toward working with ChildRescue in all piloting exercises. While certain aspects of the solution were rated and partly criticised in the surveys – so the quantitative part of the evaluation – the qualitative data paint a different picture in the general attitude toward ChildRescue. All piloting organisations stressed the potential to ease workflows and improve upon their existing techniques by the additional use of ChildRescue but used the opportunity of the surveys to pinpoint further potential for even more improvement of the app and platform in the state that it was presented to them.

2.3 Implementation of the Feedback

The technical partners of the consortium studied and prioritised the feedback resulting from both the pilots' field exercise (M30) and the feedback/effects of the public launch (M31), as it is recorded in D4.5. These contributed to a modified and improved ChildRescue solution. The two following sections describe in technical detail the modifications implemented in the mobile application, as well as the web platform of ChildRescue.

2.3.1 Technical modification of the App

The large scale nature of the piloting exercises and the fact that they took place under real circumstances provided with valuable feedback regarding the implementation of a set of features both in the community mobile app as well as in the volunteers' mobile app, which enhance the user experience, improve the reliability and the performance of the apps and also extend the functionality already provided to the community and volunteers.

The following list provides the main updates that took place in the community mobile app and the volunteers' mobile app.

Table 2-23 Mobile app updates after the pilots

Category	Feature	Community app	Volunteers app
Case management	Follow case automatically when a user views alert to ensure that the close message will be sent to all users who received the alert initially	yes	yes
	Display closed cases in dashboard for a certain period of time	yes	yes
	Retrieve the last alert description for case description	yes	yes
User experience	Improve content translations	yes	yes
	Provide UI enhancements (date picker in registration form, validation messages, font resize, etc.)	yes	yes
	Improve navigation in the mobile app (new UI implementation)	yes	yes
	Addition of filter of active cases per organisation	yes	yes
	Send a thank you message to registered users every 3 months to further engage the community	yes	n/a
	Provide "Forgot password" functionality	yes	yes

	Enable photo preview in cases	yes	yes
User profile	Addition of profile details	yes	yes
	Ability to edit user profile	yes	yes
User privacy	Access of terms of use through the menu	yes	yes
	Reminder that the (registered) user will share his/her details upon submitting his/her feedback	yes	n/a
Notifications	Optimising notification geofencing in iOS	yes	n/a
Team management	Communication channel between the Network manager and the team leader	n/a	yes
Performance	Improving application scalability with Firebase upon alert broadcast	yes	Yes

2.3.2 Technical modification of the Platform

The technical modifications of the Platform, after the original release, came into five successive versions as follows:

Table 2-2-24 Platform updates after the pilots

Release	Description of modification	Type
1.0.5 (December 2020)	Finalised Translations in Platform.	Improvement
	Ability to send alerts to volunteers only	Improvement
	Restricted Alerts to be targeted only within the country of the respective organisation	Improvement
	Improvements in UI	Improvement
	Fixed linked cases to show correctly.	Fix
	Minor bug-fixing and text corrections.	Fix
1.0.4 (November 2020)	Notify all Case Managers on incoming new fact by sending an E-mail (proved more efficient solution since you can be informed even if you are on the street or at home via your mobile phone).	Improvement
	The "country" field was added and is now configurable upon creation of an Organisation, so that it is sent to the mobile app when needed.	Improvement
	Added number of Archived cases to the Org. Manager dashboard.	Improvement
	Fixed Download button (PDF) in Fact pop-up window.	Fix
	Most of the Control Room parameters (check boxes, zoom levels, etc) are not affected anymore by the auto-refresh	Fix
	Minor bug-fixing.	Fix
1.0.3 (October 2020)	Dashboard added for Organisation Owner and Coordinator	Improvement
	Improvements in UI	Improvement
	Registered User's contact details (name, phone, email) are now shown in facts list (on hover)	Improvement
	NEW facts in pending status are now marked differently until someone views them and changes status.	Improvement
	Removed limit from alert duration field.	Fix
	Removed text limit from some case fields (physical charac-	Fix

	teristics).	
	Fixed "Forget password" functionality.	Fix
	Fixed PDF (created from Fact) where long text was dropping out of the page.	Fix
	Problem with fact's incident time was addressed.	Fix
1.0.2 (September 2020)	Enabled Auto-refresh in most of the case tabs contents (volunteers, facts, map, analytics).	Improvement
	Enabled a Preview of Alert before sending.	Improvement
	Ability to duplicate an Alert.	Improvement
	Ability to deactivate all alerts with a single button.	Improvement
	Added option to "share" case with other organisations (appears in Search results of other Organisation, in -view only-mode).	Improvement
	Made feed posts available to be sent to specific groups or individuals (volunteers).	Improvement
	Improvements in UI.	Improvement
	Fixed user authentication if user already existed.	Fix
	Other Bug fixing.	Fix
1.0.1 (July 2020)	Replaced number value with meaningful text in fact evaluation.	Improvement
	Added 'haircut' field as a new item in case details.	Improvement
	Added 'petit' to available options in Body type case field.	Improvement
	Add custom text message to be sent on Close Case.	Improvement
	Added toggle Analytics checkbox.	Improvement
	Fixed Avatar issue in organisation profile.	Fix
	Fixed infinity values that were appearing in some analytics results	Fix
	Other Bug fixing.	Fix

In addition to these, a clone of the platform was deployed in a separate server environment, in order to accommodate dissemination/exploitation activities by demonstrating the functionalities of the ChildRescue solution to external organisations that are provided with a demo account.

3 Review of used theoretical concepts

When establishing the essential information for cases of missing children in a scientifically based manner to create reliable activity and behaviour profiles of children, it is vital to consider the state-of-the-art research and opinions of experts in the field while grounding these findings in appropriately chosen theories. In order to appropriately discuss the phenomenon of missing children in the face of different legal definitions in different European countries, it is vital to adhere to the differentiation of cases that was proposed by Missing Children Europe (MCE), which distinguishes between Runaways, abductions by third persons, international parental abductions and missing unaccompanied migrant minors. This classification has been at the heart of the theories that were selected for the ChildRescue project. The selection of theories presented in D2.1 and D2.4 have been validated through the data from both the interviews conducted for D2.1 as well as the data acquired in the first and second piloting phase. Further, the additional information on unaccompanied migrant minors that was added in D2.5 served to paint a more accurate picture of the differences between the categories of missing children as they were presented and used as the theoretical basis for the development of the templates for the app and platform. Therefore, the chosen theories can be substantiated and held up throughout the rollout of the project. Additional literature, which has been fed into the presentations and papers that were created during ChildRescue, has further shown the benefit of differentiating the missing children cases into categories to prioritise different information according to the circumstances of the disappearance. However, the risk of an accidental misclassification remains, which can have negative outcomes for the successful resolution of the missing child's case. In the case of misclassification, information that is not essential might be prioritised or, as the potential worst outcome, wrong places of interest for the child could be deducted and the alarm, hence, sent to the wrong area, which renders the alarm useless. However, the current work progress in the UK was described in the interview conducted with a UK police officer for D2.1 to be based on a risk assessment, which included the possibility to class missing children as 'no apparent risk', which can lead to no action being taken for some days. Additionally, the current workflows as presented in the interviews conducted for D2.1 and the first focus groups do not allow for a swift and effective information exchange between NGOs or with the public, since the public announcements of missing children through TV or radio is usually time-delayed because of the work process in these media outlets. Therefore, the misclassification, even in its worst-case scenario, is still an improvement in comparison to the current state of the art.

There was a multitude of selected theories that were presented in D2.1 in order to appropriately address all cases of missing children in a theorised context (cf. table 3-1). The additional information on the usefulness and applicability of these theories to the different case categories shall be discussed below to showcase the lessons learnt throughout the project.

Table 3-1: Theories selected for the different types of missing children cases

Categories of missing children cases and theories	
Missing children case type	Theories (examples)
Runaways	Subcultural Theory, Activity Theory, Social Network Analysis
Third-person abductions	Social Network Theory, Victimology
Parental Abductions	Activity Theory, Social Network Analysis
Missing unaccompanied migrant minors	Subcultural Theory, Activity Theory, Collective Behaviour Theory
Lost, injured or otherwise missing child	Not applicable due to lack of information on the case

3.1 System theories

System theories analyse the environment of an individual to explain their behaviour and thus identify correlations between environment and person. In missing children cases, this is especially vital when the child has not been taken by another person and thus has retained a certain degree of agency, so can be classified as a Runaway or a case of a missing unaccompanied migrant minor. In those cases, the environment of the child that has gone missing can hold important information about the location of the child as minors sometimes join pre-existing networks of other Runaway youths. Due to the high importance of informal information during the migration decision-making process, other minors may also be vital information sources in cases of the disappearance of unaccompanied migrant minors. Since there is a lack of a homogenous legal framework in the EU member states in cases of missing unaccompanied migrant minors as displayed in the white paper that was published in the course of ChildRescue, their fast recovery is crucial, in order to avoid confusion and the consequent delay in action when international actors are involved. Hence, the importance of system theories such as the action theory, collective behaviour theory, social network analysis and subcultural theory that were chosen in D2.1 and confirmed in D2.5 have proven their worth for the understanding of these cases and the children's behaviour in both the academic understanding of the phenomenon as well as the practical applications as reported throughout both piloting phases.

3.2 Victimology

Victimology sheds light on the characteristics of these missing children that display a low level of agency. While the system theories mostly serve to explain instances of missing children in which the child has a high degree of agency albeit limited behavioural choices, the cases of low agency, especially third-person abductions, cannot fully be explained by solely focussing on the social system of the victim as most of the activity is influenced by the perpetrator rather than the victim. However, focussing on factors of vulnerability for becoming a victim can shed light on the probability that an incident of a missing child falls under the category of third-person abduction. While there are certain risk factors that can suggest a third-person abduction as the most likely scenario, such as the young

age of the child and a healthy family dynamic, other possibilities should also be taken into consideration. Therefore, victimology has some benefits for understanding the common features of older and current cases that may be helpful in resolving these cases faster. However, when cases are regarded singularly, without a connection with older cases, the applicability of victimology is extremely limited. Yet, in the context of ChildRescue, which also employs algorithms that enable machine learning, this theory may serve to explain recurring patterns in similar cases that may be missed otherwise. Therefore, victimology is a sensible addition to the system theories and can help in cases where the system theories alone would not lead to a satisfying result.

3.3 Computational Based Theories for Activity and Behaviour Analysis

A large part of WP2 was devoted to the investigation of computational based theories regarding the activity and behaviour analysis of humans, which could be applied to children, and therefore, ChildRescue. The study of these theories, helped us in two ways: first, to identify the most appropriate indicators that could form a basic profile of a missing child case, and second, to apply the most appropriate algorithms for data analysis that could offer valuable insights and predictions.

Table 3-2. List of theories applied in ChildRescue

Theories	Applied on:
Subcultural Theory, Activity Theory, Social Network Analysis, Victimology, Collective Behaviour Theory	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The extraction of indicators of a "missing child case" profile - The establishment of a categorisation of 5 typical profiles
Computational Learning, Profiling (information science)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Profile modelling (5 models) - Profile estimation of a new case based on past cases - Search for similar past cases - Evaluation of initial possible destinations - Evaluation of incoming information
Human Mobility Behaviour, Probability Theory, Collective Intelligence Theory	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Next POI evaluation through crowd validation - The estimation of search areas and locations to send alerts - The computation of movement direction for the missing child

It should be noted here that Activity profiling based on the analysis of missing children social networks presence (e.g. his/her recent Facebook posts, his/her tweets, etc.) was partially hindered due to personal data involvement and the restrictions provided by the GDPR. This was addressed by using manual input from social workers related to their estimation of the social presence of the child, which did not involve any personal details.

As is usually the case, the application of theories on real-world data goes along with a range of challenges. ChildRescue was not an exception. The most important of these challenges is extensively described in D2.5. In any case, the purpose of ChildRescue and the theories applied is to assist in a

missing child investigation by organising and accelerating the involved procedures. Additionally, it should lead to a more efficient approach when managing unaccompanied migrant minors in hosting facilities. Both have been accomplished successfully with respect to data protection and privacy.

However, an important lesson learnt is that each child is unique, and thus cannot be treated based solely on past cases and experiences from other children. Most social workers and rescue team members agree that a hidden factor in a child's psychology or a tiny detail that affects the child's current mindset can turn a case into an unpredictable sequence of events. Therefore, any attempt to provide predictions or to classify a case into a missing child type should be handled with extreme care, making clear to the recipients of the information that any predictive results, are the computational products of data correlations which indicate only probability and not certainty.

4 Impact assessment

In order to evaluate the impact of ChildRescue, the fulfilment of the technical KPIs shall be considered as well as the further dissemination of project results and the impact that ChildRescue has had on the workflow in the respective piloting organisations. This last point is of crucial importance since it hints at the potential to improve the reaction to disappearances of children through the use of ChildRescue.

4.1 Technical KPIs

The delivery of the ChildRescue platform is based on the implementation of novel, self-standing components and their integration under a common platform. This is translated into two technical objectives. The first has to do with the seamless integration of data coming from heterogeneous sources and the second with the building of an open-source, value-adding platform that supports the ChildRescue methodology. Each of these objectives is assessed based on a number of indicators (KPIs), each one with a target value. The following table presents the technical KPIs (as set initially in the DoA) along with their target value and the achieved value at the end of the project.

Table 4-1 Technical KPIs with reached values

	Requirement (KPI)	Target Value	Reached Value	Comments
[OBJ.5] Create connectors and interfaces to third-party systems	# of open data sources	>=10	10	OpenStreetMap, Google Map, OpenWeather-Map, OASA telematics API (Athens bus company), The MIVB/STIB API (Brussels bus company), navitia.io (open "public transport" api), data.gov.gr, data.gov.be, data.europa.eu, kaggle
	# of social networks connectors	>=3	3	Foursquare API, Eventful API, Twitter Search API
	# of interfaces to open, linked data infrastructures	>=3	0	<i>Considered: EU open data portal, dbpedia.org, wikidata.org, grid.ac</i>
	# of legacy systems	4	0	<i>Considered: SoC (legacy db, EKAS, SMS service notifications), REDCROSS (legacy db), CHILD FOCUS (CMS)</i>
[OBJ.6] Link User Requirements to Technical Requirements	# of generic requirements	>=20	49	Recorded in D3.1 (25 for scenario 1 and 24 for scenario 2). There are also 137 user stories included in D3.4.
	# of readily available components considered	5	7	Android 8.0 mobile framework (android oreo), Firebase Cloud Messaging, LocationManager, Geocoder, Django web framework, Django REST framework, PostgreSQL
	# of APIs	7	9	Case Manager, Collaboration Space, Control Room, Privacy & Anonymisation Engine, Intelligent Search Engine, Profiling & Prediction Engine, Evaluation Engine, Communication Engine, Data Harmonisation & Interoperability Space
	# of ChildRescue components to be integrated	7	12	Case Manager, Collaboration Space, Control Room, Privacy & Anonymisation Engine, Intelligent Search Engine, Profiling & Prediction Engine, Evaluation Engine, Communication Engine, Data Harmonisation & Interoperability Space, Blockchain, ChildRescue Community Mobile app, ChildRescue Volunteer Mobile app
	# of mobile applications	1	3	ChildRescue Community (Android + iOS), ChildRescue Volunteers (Android)
	# of management interfaces	1	5	Case Manager, Organisation Owner, Organisation Coordinator, Network Manager, ChildRescue Admin
	# of GitHub repositories	1 with >=50 stars	2 with total >=50 stars	There are additionally 3 repositories in GitLab, one for each of the mobile app versions.

Notes regarding the technical KPIs

Nearly all target values were achieved. Further clarification is needed in following topics a clarification is required, as follows:

- **For the open data sources**, a number of third-party data sources were examined during the development of the ChildRescue solution. Some of them had to do with public datasets of the past, while others were related to online geodata or weather data sources. Out of them,

the ChildRescue solution currently utilises three, namely OpenStreetMap³, OpenWeatherMap⁴ and Google Maps⁵. The first two are used for extracting transportation infrastructure and weather details, respectively, that allows for more accurate computations regarding the whereabouts of a missing child. Google Maps were employed to extend the UI functionality and visualise geographic information (geodata) for both the platform and mobile applications. For the rest of the sources, while the connections were developed and tested, they ultimately found no use under the scenarios supported by the current version of the platform. It is worth mentioning at this point, that no datasets related to missing children cases or unaccompanied migrant minors were available in public data repositories, apart from some statistical reports with information usually aggregated per country and year. Localised criminal activity data, that could be of some use, were also unavailable for the piloting countries.

- **For the social network connectors**, the original idea in DoA was for the platform to be able to connect to social media platforms and extract data from the profile of the child and its friends (always with consent from parents or guardians), which was technically feasible at the time. After the enforcement of GDPR, however, the available APIs that would allow this, either ceased to function or the retrieval of any personal data was prohibited. To overcome this challenge, ChildRescue turned to a different approach regarding social network connectors: to receive non-personal data from social networks that are related to events and popular venues, like Foursquare, Eventful and Twitter. However, during the pilot testing, twitter results were found to clutter the system with useless information, and therefore they are currently not exposed to the End-users.
- **For the open, linked data**, the implementation explored four popular databases (which seemed more relevant to the context of the project when it comes to information that could be used from them), in particular the EU open data portal⁶, DBpedia⁷, Wikidata⁸ and GRID⁹. The available topics and terms, however, were hardly related to ChildRescue. Additionally, there were language restrictions, since linked data are mostly available in English. Therefore, under these circumstances, no exploitation of linked data could be performed in the implementation of ChildRescue.
- **Regarding the legacy systems** of the pilot partners, due to data protection issues, it was decided not to develop such connectors. Nevertheless, after the second pilot exercise in M30, Child Focus expressed the willingness to examine the possibility, which might lead to post-project discussions and activities.

³ <https://www.openstreetmap.org>

⁴ <https://openweathermap.org/>

⁵ <https://cloud.google.com/maps-platform/maps>

⁶ <https://data.europa.eu/euodp/en/data/>

⁷ <https://wiki.dbpedia.org/>

⁸ <https://www.wikidata.org/>

⁹ <https://www.grid.ac/>

4.2 Dissemination

The final year of the project in 2020 posed unforeseen challenges due to the COVID-19 pandemic which was declared by the World Health Organisation (WHO) in March 2020. As a result, the dissemination, communication and stakeholder plans had to compromise. Thus, the project's strategy had to change and adapt to the circumstances. Due to lockdown restrictions across Europe including Belgium and Greece (the first countries piloting ChildRescue) travelling and face-to-face-meetings were not possible and alternatively digitalised forms of communication and cooperation had to be established.

Despite these challenges, the public launch could take place on 28th of July, 2020 (in Greece, with all partners) and on 28th of August, 2020 (for Belgium, Child Focus), and the working group achieved positive outcomes (over 15K downloads upon both launches) in such a short period of time and considering the circumstances. (Refer to D5.6 "Dissemination, Communication and Stakeholder Engagement Report, Final Release", for further details on dissemination actions and results.)

4.3 Impact on piloting organisations

Through the implementation of ChildRescue in the piloting organisations, different consequences for their workflows have emerged, which shall be discussed individually.

4.3.1 Impact on workflow in SoC

It is worth mentioning that both the ChildRescue app and the platform are supplementary to the existing tools and processes that the organisation already uses.

The two key impacts for the workflow of the organisation, as identified after the pilots' implementation and the official launch in July 2020, are the following:

1. Facilitation of communication among 116000 operators and citizens.

One major advantage of the adoption of the app by SoC is that it enables communication among the 116000 operators and the public. Before ChildRescue, every citizen that had received information of a missing child's case needed to call 116000 and provide the relevant information only by phone. The 116000 operators evaluated the information given (relevant, irrelevant, credible etc.) and followed the processes described above. The adoption of the ChildRescue platform and app offers the opportunity for citizens to provide direct information through the app without having to call the 116000 operators. Also, the operators maintain a record of feedback from citizens also having the ability to mark their evaluation in the platform (relevant, irrelevant, credible etc.) Additionally, apart from sending messages via the app, citizens can send location information and media (e.g. images, video) via the app. In that meaning, the app facilitates direct communication that can be faster than the existing procedure and critical for finding a child. Of course, this process might be hindered by the citizen's unwillingness to download the app, since the communication by phone might be easier for a large number of citizens. Also, to be taken into account is the fact that Greece has a share of 61,6% of smartphone users compared to 77,3% in Belgium [1, 2].

2. Facilitation of communication among 116000 operators and the coordinator of the Search and Rescue Team of SoC (Network Manager)

Although fortunately, none of the real cases uploaded in the app so far demanded the activation of the Search & Rescue team, the app facilitates the communication among 116000 operators and the coordinator of the Search & Rescue team (Network Manager). As described above, the existing pro-

cess is that the communication among the 116000 operators (case managers) and the coordinator of the Search & Rescue team (network manager) is only conducted by phone. The Search and Rescue team coordinator informs the 116000 operators on the team's location and relevant findings. The use of the ChildRescue platform and app enables communication among the network manager and the case managers in terms that it can be implemented directly through the app without phone communication.

To conclude, the ChildRescue platform and app will be used as a supplementary tool to the existing processes, offering to the organisation's involved departments (116000 operators & Search and Rescue Team) improved information sharing, time management and effective coordination.

4.3.2 Impact on workflow in Child Focus

During the development of the ChildRescue platform, application and its workflows, Child Focus, together with the other pilot partners, carefully watched over the fact that it had to coincide with the, at that time, existing workflow and procedures. Therefore, integrating ChildRescue into their workflows appears to be easier.

However, this did need a lot of reflection and considerations. Dealing with missing children's cases, launching public appeals and collecting information from the public and share these with police services is a complex machinery at Child Focus. In order to pick-up speed when launching (paper or digital via social networks of digital structural partners), Child Focus permanently has five people on call: Case manager for follow-up of the case, hotline operator for testimonies, Group 1 who creates the appeal image, Group 2 who ensures printing and Group 3 who activates the network of volunteers to hang out the paper posters. When integrating ChildRescue into their procedures, it had to be decided who will take up which role.

Another important point of reflection was in which cases Child Focus would use ChildRescue. Annually Child Focus launches public appeals in about 10% of the missing children's cases reported to Child Focus. Child Focus very carefully outweighs the need to share information with the general public. A child's privacy is of major importance. Thus, putting the child's face, information on the identity and physical features to the general public, because the child went missing has to be always very carefully weighed up with the actual need to share this type of information with the public to find the child as quickly as possible against the child's privacy rights.

Child Focus has many different options in the way to launch public appeals: from very public such as launching a Child Alert as the broadest option to very discrete flyers for target groups such as shop keepers, employees in the transport sector, social workers, etc. Here the information is not further distributed, but kept 'under the counter'.

Between the second pilot in June 2020 and the launch in September 2020, Child Focus integrated ChildRescue in their workflow and procedures. Today, a ChildRescue alert is deployed at the same level as a social media message and / or a paper poster campaign on a local level. So if, after consultation with the police and the magistrate, it is decided that is in the best interest of the child to launch a public appeal via social media and / or a local poster campaign, they simultaneously launch a ChildRescue alert in the area relevant for the investigation. This activation is initiated by the Case Manager, who shares the information needed with the member of Group 3 on call. The Group 3-member will launch the alert on ChildRescue. Afterwards, the hotline operator on call takes over to monitor the facts and information that comes in. They retrieve this information from the platform and share it with the competent police services dealing with the case. The case manager follows-up all

information linked to the case, also the ones coming in through ChildRescue and remains in permanent contact with the parents and police services. The case manager syncs with the Group 3 manager in any changes or adaptations that have to be made such as launching a new alert in a different area if needed or de-activating the alert when the child is found.

This workflow is being tested since the launch of ChildRescue, so from the beginning of September 2020, gradually involving more people (from one fixed Group 3 member to the whole team of four people or one fixed Hotline operator to the full group of ten). Up until today, this workflow appears to be efficient and useful. An in-depth evaluation will be undertaken at the beginning of 2021 in order to capture whether internal adjustments/ improvements are required.

Although real cases testing is always uncertain, given the fact that we 'have to work with' actual cases coming in, within the first three months of operational use of ChildRescue, Child Focus already had the opportunity to test and explore its added value in cross-border cases. Although not being neighbouring countries, the two pilot countries for missing children, Belgium and Greece, shared a case. A young boy entered Belgium through Zaventem Airport, coming from Greece. He went missing in Belgium, whilst his accompanying adult returned to Greece. Ever since there is no trace of the boy, so we do not know whether he is in Belgium or Greece. The case was reported to Child Focus and followed the normal procedures. When the case manager, together with Child Focus law enforcement partners, decided to launch a public appeal, including a ChildRescue-alert, Child Focus also contacted their Greek colleagues and asked to spread a call for information in Greece. Child Focus created the case on the ChildRescue platform and could use the 'share'-option of the platform to share the case with Smile of the Child. In Belgium, an alert was launched. In Greece, as soon as the phone and e-mail communication was completed, the case manager of SoC duplicated and uploaded the case in the app to be able to handle the case. Also, the picture of the boy was published to SoC's social media. SoC's case manager also contacted the SIRENE department (Hellenic Police Department responsible for locating missing children, among others). After a series of e-mail communication with Child Focus between the case managers, the case manager of SoC asked Child Focus to refer the case to the SIRENE in Belgium. Unfortunately, up until today, there is no trace of the boy.

4.3.3 Impact on workflow in REDCROSS

It is important to underline that the REDCROSS Movement follows very specific procedures with regard to the treatment of UMC and missing children cases and as a result, the use of ChildRescue can only be complementary to those procedures.

The main concerns had to do with the data protection issues and the legal implications, given that the REDCROSS pilot is dedicated to UMC and there are certain restrictions deriving from the relative Movement legacy. The guardianship of the UMC in Greece remains a key issue and social workers working with the REDCROSS shelters underlined that the validation of data use should probably be on a state level. It is also noted that ChildRescue could offer a great opportunity to unify data on different organisational levels, i.e. internally in the organisation. However, there is a concern on how sharing of information with other organisations would work.

According to the initial planning, REDCROSS was expected to introduce the ChildRescue registration of UMC with the REDCROSS facilities accommodating UMC during the piloting of the project. That was based on a vague assumption that there will be no contradiction to the overall procedure followed during the reception of the children in the REDCROSS facilities. In reality, the posting and the reception of the UMC with the REDCROSS hosting facilities also involve state and non-state actors who are

not part of the project and again the registration of the UMC with the ChildRescue can be the case only under conditions: complimentary to the regular procedures and with the consent of the children involved. That in many cases, duplicates the work needed for the facility managers. Moreover, there has been a slight difference in the time intervals between the disappearance and the data extraction of the UMC from the facility records, since the initial planning and that has a direct impact on the validity of the registered in an active investigation. As a result, and because of the above, the REDCROSS introduced the registration of UMC above 16 years old with three REDCROSS facilities with a slight delay and the analysis on time intervals is expected together with the finalisation of the project. Consequently, the ChildRescue platform aims to be used in parallel to the REDCROSS mechanisms offering a new asset to the organisation's multidisciplinary approach towards a more efficient and effective solution for UMC, by contributing to the prevention of disappearance, improving time management and providing a tool that will reinforce coordination, decision making and information sharing on different organisational levels (hosting facilities, Tracing Service, Management, regional REDCROSS Departments, etc.).

4.4 Challenges and Impact beyond the project

The outbreak of the Covid-19 pandemic required adaptations in the planned procedures of the piloting phase. While the first evaluation phase with the tabletop exercises could be held as planned, the second piloting exercise had to be adapted to the changed circumstances. Mainly, the planned real-life testing of a mock case with actors on the streets could not be rolled out as planned due to the lockdown and accompanying limitations on the number of people that could meet each other in person. Instead, the piloting exercises had to be changed in a digital version of mock cases. As a consequence, training of and evaluation by participants had to be carried out virtually with consequences such as discussed in section 2.2.

Yet, throughout the rollout of ChildRescue, the academic partners could contribute to the scarce knowledge of missing children in a meaningful way. More than five publications and 17 presentations on different international conferences have been compiled which have added to the state-of-the-art knowledge on the subject. Covid-19 pandemic had, however, also an impact on these actions, since, for both academic partners, FRA-UAS and NTUA, conferences in which they would participate to present their work in the context of ChildRescue were cancelled.

A White Paper [3] on the complicated and disadvantaged situation of missing unaccompanied migrant minors in comparison to other missing children in the EU has been composed, which has contributed to reducing the severe gap of knowledge on this vulnerable group. Results show that there is more research needed on topics such as understanding the motivation and circumstances of these disappearances and further issues throughout the European the member states and internationally. In the course of ChildRescue, there was an exchange with experts on the topics. However, it was not possible to conduct interviews with victims – (formerly) missing children themselves or their families, thus missing their perspective in the project.

For future research, participatory designs could be another approach in order to grasp the situation of children before and during their disappearance and achieve deeper insights in order to develop preventative programs. The situation of missing unaccompanied migrant minors is even more complex as it also requires insights in transnational procedures and processes. The merits of ChildRescue are the

theoretical based approach which takes into consideration the different categories of missing children, the continuous exchange with practice partners in the development of the app and the platform, the deep insight into the work practise and required adaptations and the continuously evaluated product which proved to have a variety of benefits for the work process, thus contributing for quicker information leading to a quicker finding of missing children.

Furthermore, while public engagement and broad participation of citizens is an ongoing business challenge for ChildRescue, the quantification of this engagement, namely the minimum number of users that need to use the ChildRescue application for it to deliver the promised results and work significantly better than existing solutions, is a research challenge that ChildRescue is also engaging with and attempts to solve. In particular, a simulation environment has been developed by NTUA that could create an easy-to-reconfigure concept of effectiveness for the ChildRescue mobile application. The simulation uses agent-based modelling [4] for its development. Since every city consists of residential areas, industrial zones, commercial districts and other types of neighbourhoods, we have acknowledged that each geographic area examined has its distinct mobility characteristics, reflecting its inhabitants' daily lives. Therefore, the answer on the minimum number of ChildRescue users needed is not a single number, but it should be examined separately for each different city, municipality or neighbourhood. In this context, the simulation environment developed is easily reconfigurable to distinct geographic areas and adaptable to the different scalability needs.

In Figure 4-1, the suggested approach based on the developed simulation environment is presented. On the left, the input that the system needs to work successfully is depicted. This input refers to the identification of the mobility patterns of the city or neighbourhood examined, as a result of an analysis of data from this area. The extracted patterns from the mobility analysis are exploited as input for the system, configuring its parameters. Then, in the centre, a screenshot of the simulation model is presented. The screenshot here refers to the centre of Athens in Greece. The model consists of (a) a specific geographical area, along with its building, roads and a set of other geographical information included in the motion graph of the simulation, (b) people agents, i.e. the users of the ChildRescue mobile application, where several parameters are applied to them, defining the way they are commuting, as derived from the previous analysis and (c) the missing child, along with a set of information and adjustable parameters for him/her. Finally, on the right, a display of the monitors that the user can see while the simulation is running is shown, including a diagram for the number of times people agents of the system approached the missing child.

Figure 4-1 The ChildRescue suggested solution for addressing the question on the minimum number of ChildRescue application users needed.

This approach has been submitted and will be published as a book chapter in a new edited book entitled "HANDBOOK OF RESEARCH ON ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE, INNOVATION AND ENTREPRENEURSHIP" which will be published by Edward Elgar Publishing. Experimentation on this environment for different geographic areas is currently in progress, and its results will be submitted for publishing as a journal article in the forthcoming period.

5 Planned further exploitation of ChildRescue

SoC

Regarding SoC, the impact already identified is the facilitation of the communication among 116000 operators and citizens on the one hand and the communication among the 116000 operators and the Search & Rescue Coordinator. ChildRescue app functionalities that can be further explored are related to the organisation of the communication of the Search and Rescue Team members and also cross-border cases of missing children on the condition that further modifications of the app are implemented.

Even though the activation of the Search & Rescue Team was tested during the field exercise, there was no real active case within the organisation in which it was necessary to involve the Search & Rescue Team. The functionality of the ChildRescue app to invite new volunteers will give the organisation the opportunity to employ them differently than before. Also, if further modifications are implemented, there will be a possibility to manage different groups of volunteers, and also the coordinator and the team leaders will be able to communicate directly with each other as well as with the volunteers. The various chat rooms among the different groups of volunteers and the team leaders and also the live tracking system, two features that are currently not available, will constitute an added value to the app's usage by the organisation.

Furthermore, pilot organisations may benefit from the use of the ChildRescue app in cross-border cases like the one that was tested between the two piloting organisations in Belgium and Greece.

Child Focus

Child Focus launched its first ChildRescue Alert on September 9th 2020. The beginning of an era of which the Child Focus partners strongly believe it will be a paradigm change in the search for missing children in Belgium. In the months and weeks after the launch, Child Focus and ChildRescue consortium in total continued to learn, explore and improve. The first experiences are more than positive: the speed with which Child Focus can launch very local, so very relevant alerts is impressively low compared with their, however, very well-oiled and efficient, machinery for paper posters or flyers. The threshold for sharing relevant information with Child Focus by the general public is much lower.

As described above, the current integration in Child Focus procedures and workflow will be evaluated and if needed, adapted in January 2021. Up until now, Child Focus uses the 'basic features' to create cases, launch (and adapt) alerts, gather facts and information from the general public. After a first evaluation, Child Focus will roll-out an action plan for a more in-depth integration and elaboration of ChildRescue in their daily practice:

- Detailed use of the machine learning and predictive algorithms provided by ChildRescue to match old with new cases and retrieve similar data across cases
- Child Focus uses the collaborative working space for volunteers in a slightly different way compared to SoC, since they do not have search and rescue teams.
- The collaborative working space was tested during the second pilot and was estimated very useful for coordinating with volunteers. If a ChildRescue alert coincides with a distribution of paper posters or flyers, this could not yet be integrated in their daily practice. One important factor is the training of volunteers in using the app. Because of the Covid-pandemic, Child Focus will not be able to provide such training as it would require face-to-face contact. Therefore, this aspect of ChildRescue will be adopted in 2021.

- Think out of the box, especially when it comes to Child Focus 'structural' partners for, for instance, flyers. Today, in some cases, they distribute discrete flyers to, for instance, all Securitas security guards. Although a very efficient process, the time needed to develop the flyer and distribute it to all security agents in a certain area, is considerable. Maybe we can see them as a specific group of 'volunteers' that we can reach through the collaborative working space. Maybe the application and platform offer other options that can be useful.

Last but not least, as Belgium is a small country, Child Focus sometimes deals with cross-border cases. It already was the case during the real cases testing-period, so ChildRescue provided them with the opportunity to share information on the case in a very easy manner (cf. above). If Child Focus neighbouring countries, as well as other European partners, would also be using ChildRescue, this could facilitate collaboration in these cross-border cases in exchanging information but also in launching joint alerts for children who went missing and might be located in another country, as well as gathering information from the general public in both Belgium and the other country.

In any case, Child Focus is determined to assure that ChildRescue is known among the Belgian general public. They have invested a lot of resources in communicating on the app since its launch on August 30th 2020. With by now over 15.000 downloads for only Belgium, Child Focus is already more than happy with the coverage at this stage. For assuring full operation, they strive for a total of at least 25.000 downloads for Belgium alone. So communication efforts will not cease to exist after the end of the project but will continue in 2021 and beyond.

REDCROSS

The Hellenic Red Cross participation is distinct to that of the other partners and in line to the fundamental Principles of the International Red Cross and Red Crescent Movement and the Red Cross code of conduct with regard to child protection and data management. The REDCROSS participation to the project focuses on the UMC with the aim to enabling safe, discreet and quick procedures in regards to both their registration and the research of UMC under predefined conditions but, also to increase child protection capacity, at least on a national level, while the international nature of the organisation opens a window for a cross border utilisation of the ChildRescue platform.

Today, communication with and among REDCROSS volunteers is mainly done by phone, which restricts the types and the immediacy of information that can be shared. Real-time information sharing -including photos and multimedia- and location monitoring, although not tested with the REDCROSS yet, could provide new potential to volunteer mobilisation and coordination and might also contribute to improving cross border cooperation in the near future.

An overall evaluation is that ChildRescue can be a useful and discreet registration tool in case it is more widely adopted. In such a case, the sharing functionality of data elements of ChildRescue can contribute a lot to the advancement of child protection in Greece. Moreover, the research aspects of ChildRescue are considered to be very useful for the mobilisation and the follow up of selected and trained REDCROSS volunteers and also support multiple types of research. The REDCROSS has already presented ChildRescue to the Movement components, and they expect for the final product to be offered in order to be evaluated for further use on Movement's level.

Last but not least, it should always be noted, when it comes to broader exploitation and communication purposes, the following disclaimer:

Hellenic Red Cross participation is in full compliance with the International Red Cross/Red Crescent Movement Fundamental Principles and restrictions in regards to publishing and sharing information and personal data.

Access to REDCROSS information is possible only to users certified by the Organisation. The National Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies all around the globe engage only trained and certified volunteers.

6 Future Technical Modifications Planning

Since the public launch of the ChildRescue application in late July 2020 (M31), the requests for changes and additional features were many, coming from the involved pilot partners, as well as simple citizens. This is an extremely healthy reaction for an innovative solution and shows, in a way, the positive impact it can have on the community.

Some of the suggested modifications were feasible to be addressed within the project's duration and scope, some were not. This section is dedicated to the latter and presents a list of technical recommendations and new features that can work as a guide for future modifications (i.e. after the end of the project). Some of them require a lot of effort, and some others, while trivial, form a group of requests that target a specific role or particular functionality. All of them, nevertheless, aim to improve and extend the functionalities of the overall ChildRescue solution.

Table 6-1: Recommended Modifications for the ChildRescue Solution

Modification/Improvement	Related Component
Allow for multiple photos of a child to be stored and sent in Alerts	Platform
Ability for Managers to edit/delete posts in collaboration space	Platform
Ability for Case Manager to create a timeline of events	Platform
Ability to mark information as important and highlight it in a way that all other managers become aware of it	Platform
Allow for multiple searches of multiple children on the same map	Platform/ Mobile Volunteer App
Addition of layers on the map, more icons, different colours per event	Platform/ Mobile Volunteer App
When a case is closed, remove the invitation acceptance from volunteer's phone	Platform/ Mobile Volunteer App
Remove pending inactive invitations to volunteers when no longer needed	Platform/ Mobile Volunteer App
Ability for volunteer user to accept or reject the assignment as team leader	Platform/ Mobile Volunteer App
Set volunteers who have accepted the invitation into "stand-by" mode until they get "activated" to join a rescue team	Platform/ Mobile Volunteer App
Disable "take screenshot" functionality of mobile phones for the ChildRescue mobile app	Mobile Community App
Add a forcing mechanism to update to latest version	Mobile Apps (All) maintenance
Add a tool to analyse crash reports in iOS/Android such as Firebase Crashlytics (Maintenance related)	Mobile Apps (All) maintenance
Introduce an iOS version for volunteers mobile app	Mobile Volunteer App

7 Conclusions

D4.6 – "ChildRescue Pilot Evaluation and Lessons Learnt" reports the results of the evaluation period of the project during the first and second piloting phase and derives lessons learnt during the project.

The originally planned **ChildRescue pilot experimentation** was divided into two parts, the first and the second piloting exercises, consisting respectively of: a) simulation/tabletop exercise and b) a field exercise. Due to the Covid-19 pandemic, the introduction of ChildRescue had to be postponed and the second piloting phase was undertaken not on-site, but virtually and complemented by an additional survey on the effects of ChildRescue on work processes after implementing ChildRescue in the participating organisations had taken place.

The first pilot phase was conducted in the premises of each of the **three pilot organisations** and is documented in D4.3. By the time of the exercise, all ChildRescue components were deployed as the integrated ChildRescue platform and were prepared as needed to support the pilot execution, thus corresponding already to a **TRL 7 (system prototype demonstration in operational environment)**.

Technical partners took up the recommendations derived from the piloting exercise and adaptations were consequently implemented before the second piloting phase.

The second pilot phase was characterised by the effects of the Covid-19-pandemic. In the second pilot phase, simulated exercises with the further developed ChildRescue App and platform were carried out and are documented in D4.5. The second pilot phase was conducted during the first semester of 2020, where measures for the protection against the COVID-19 pandemic were still in place in both countries, i.e. Greece and Belgium. As a consequence, the methodology had to be adapted. By the time of the exercise, a further developed version with more functionalities of the integrated ChildRescue platform were prepared as needed to support the pilot execution, thus corresponding already to a **TRL 8 (system complete and qualified)**. Afterwards, taking the system into production for CF and SoC, with the apps being launched for the general public, the end result of the platform is that of a **TRL 9 (actual system proven in operational environment)**.

For both piloting exercises three scenarios each were provided by the pilot organisations to support the pilot operation; two for the Missing Children Emergency Case (Greece-supported by SoC and Belgium-supported by Child Focus) and one for the Discovery and Identification of Unaccompanied Minors (Greece-supported by REDCROSS). The developed scenarios were based **on true facts** to create a plausible environment, but any personal data related to the children were **carefully anonymised**. Members and staff of the pilot organisations participated in the exercise and were supported by the technical partners of ChildRescue consortium. The execution of the tabletop exercise followed the pilot guidelines provided in D4.2 for the first piloting exercise, respectively in D4.4 for the second piloting exercise.

Key findings and lessons learnt

Theoretical concepts contributed to the understanding of different categories of missing children cases and i.e., systems theory contributes to the understanding and identification of correlations between environment and persons. Computational based theories for activity and behaviour analysis contributed a) to identify the most appropriate indicators that could form a basic profile of a missing child case and b) to apply the most appropriate algorithms for data analysis that could offer valuable insights and predictions. However, an impeding factor for establishing Activity profiling to

analyse social networks presence of missing children is the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). The challenges of the application of theories on real-world data are reported in D2.5.

An important lesson learnt is that **each child is unique**, and thus cannot be treated based solely on past cases and experiences from other children. Most social workers and rescue team members agree that a hidden factor in a child's psychology or a tiny detail that affects the **child's current mindset** can turn a case into an **unpredictable sequence of events**. Thus, predictions or classifying a case into a missing child type have to be handled with care as predictive results are the computational products of data correlations which indicate probability and not certainty.

The **development of the ChildRescue App and platform was undertaken in an iterative process** taking into account the results of the evaluations carried out. The evaluation of the product and the sociotechnical system had three different time intervals and covered the assessment of ChildRescue as well as the relevant factors of the work process. The evaluation took into consideration the different circumstances and backgrounds of the three participating practise partner organisations which were located in Belgium (Child Focus) and Greece (SoC and REDCROSS).

Lessons learnt: The **mixed-methods approach** of focus groups, qualitative and quantitative survey procedures **enabled strong results for the further development** of the app and platform. Another major factor was the **well-established and direct communication** between developers, pilot and scientific partners.

All piloting organisations stressed the **potential to ease workflows** and **improve upon their existing techniques** by the additional use of ChildRescue. The surveys offered a valuable source to identify further potential for improvement of the app and platform in each state that it was presented to them.

The most important outcome is that all partners have a positive attitude and readiness to use ChildRescue in their everyday work. The ChildRescue app and platform seem to provide sufficient benefits already in this early stage of use not having unfolded the whole potential to be expected after having had more experience. Practise partners already perceived that time scales improved with respect of informing the public or the time needed for creating complete case reports. Due to the individuality of the cases, future surveys on the impact on the sociotechnical system could take into account items which consider the case variability. However, time constraints and lack of resources might inhibit lengthy studies carried out by the pilot organisations. Mandatory work processes at the REDCROSS leading to double entries in the documentation seem to be bearable due to the other (data documentation) benefits of ChildRescue.

Most target values of technical KPIs were achieved apart from GDPR restrictions for using social network connectors and legacy systems, and lack of open, linked data relevant to the ChildRescue's goals.

Despite the pandemic situation and its adverse effects on travelling and face-to-face meetings, the first public launch took place in July 2020. Outcomes are described in detail in D5.6.

The impact of ChildRescue on the socio-technical systems of the pilot organisations varies as they have different legal and organisational structures:

SoC utilises the ChildRescue app and platform supplementary to the existing tools and processes. Main advantages are the **improved information sharing, time management and effective coordination** among 116000 operators, citizens and the Search and Rescue Team of SoC. Their

further exploitation involves amongst others the acquisition of increased numbers of volunteers, thus enabling direct cooperation structures within and outside the organisation and benefits dealing with cross border cases.

Child Focus assumes that ChildRescue presents a paradigm change in the search for missing children in Belgium. The organisation has been testing the workflow since the launch of ChildRescue, so from the beginning of September 2020, gradually involving more people of the organisation. Up until today, this **workflow appears to be efficient and useful; the speed for information spreading increased**, and the threshold for sharing relevant information with Child Focus by the general public is much lower. ChildRescue also contributed to dealing with a **cross-border case** (Belgium and Greece). If ChildRescue is utilised in neighbouring and other European countries, it would facilitate collaboration in cross-border cases in many different ways. Child Focus plans an in-depth evaluation in the beginning of 2021 in order to capture whether internal adjustments/ improvements are required.

The **REDCROSS** Movement has to follow specific procedures with regard to the treatment of UMC and missing children cases, and as a result, the use of ChildRescue can only be complementary to those procedures. The ChildRescue platform offers **a new asset to the organisation's multidisciplinary approach** towards a more efficient and effective solution for UMC, by **contributing to the prevention of disappearance, improving time management and providing a tool that will reinforce coordination, decision making and information sharing on different organisational levels** (hosting facilities, Tracing Service, Management, regional REDCROSS Departments, etc.). In the future, it has to be expected that technological restrictions such as the predominant use of phones rather than smartphones will be overcome, thus enabling the utilisation of all of the ChildRescue functionalities. An overall evaluation shows that ChildRescue can be a useful and discreet registration tool when it is more widely adopted. In such a case, the sharing functionality of data elements of ChildRescue can contribute a lot to the advancement of child protection in Greece. Moreover, the research aspects of ChildRescue are considered to be very useful for the mobilisation and the follow up of selected and trained REDCROSS volunteers and also support multiple types of research. However, when it comes to broader exploitation, it has to be in full compliance with the International Red Cross/Red Crescent Movement Fundamental Principles and restrictions in regards to publishing and sharing information and personal data as well as certification requirements.

Lessons learnt: The **specific organisational context** with its legal requirements, existing tools and workflows have to be taken into account in order to achieve as much as possible out of the potential of ChildRescue. The different practise organisations differ in their target groups, work processes, technological equipment and legal and other organisational requirements. For the distribution of ChildRescue to new organisations, these aspects have to be taken into account, and specific adaptations seem to be inevitable.

More research is needed on topics such as understanding the motivation and circumstances of disappearances of unaccompanied migrant minors and further issues throughout the European member states and internationally. In the course of ChildRescue, there was an exchange with experts on these topics for all different types/categories of missing children. However, it was not possible to conduct interviews with victims – (formerly) missing children themselves or their families, thus missing their perspective in the project.

For future research, **participatory designs could complement the methodological approach in order to grasp the situation of children before and during their disappearance and achieve deeper insights in order to develop preventative programs.** It is conceivable that developed preventative programs could be implemented as new features of the ChildRescue app and platform, thus being a new instrument for social workers.

The situation of missing unaccompanied migrant minors is even more complex as it also requires insights in transnational procedures and processes. The merits of ChildRescue are the theoretical based approach which takes into consideration the different categories of missing children, the continuous exchange with practice partners in the development of the app and the platform, the deep insight into the work practise and required adaptations and the continuously evaluated product which proved to have a variety of benefits for the work process, thus contributing for quicker information leading to a quicker finding of missing children.

Public engagement and broad participation of citizens is an ongoing business challenge for ChildRescue, the quantification of this engagement, namely the minimum number of users that need to use the ChildRescue application for it to deliver the promised results and work significantly better than existing solutions, is a research challenge that ChildRescue is also engaging with and attempts to solve. NTUA developed a simulation environment that could create an easy-to-reconfigure concept of effectiveness for the ChildRescue mobile application, which takes into account the specifics of an area such as geography, mobility etc. In this context, the simulation environment developed is easily re-configurable to distinct geographic areas and adaptable to the different scalability needs.

8 Annex I: References

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